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Deliverable D5.1

Audit of Management Recommendations 2

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

This document presents the audit of a draft version of the second Management Recommendations (MRs) in the FarFish project. This MR2 draft was updated during the last months of the project considering the second audit recommendations, hence providing a more final MR within the project's lifetime. The audit process is a fundamental step for the implementation of the Results-Based Management (RBM) approach. In RBM, the resource users are directly involved in the management and decision-making process. The relevant authorities continue defining the policy goals but delegate (partly) the responsibility for the planning and implementation of the management means to attain those goals to the resource users. The auditor, as an independent third party, should be able to assess the extent to which these goals have been met (Nielsen et al., 2017). In FarFish, the auditor is enacted by a research institute. However, this role can be taken by any organization with auditing capacity or by a joint audit committee designated by both parties.

The audit of the second MRs revealed interesting results in terms of the implementation of the key activities planned for achieving the Outcome Targets (OTs). Several challenges were also found in the implementation and performance of the MRs. Some of the most common challenges referred to coordination and collaboration with the Coastal States or the acting Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO), although when this was in place, the success of the action considerably increased. As the MR of the case study (CS) 1 for the Southwest Atlantic high seas, presented the critical challenge of not having a RFMO, the MR aimed to contribute towards addressing this challenge. The CS2 for the Southeast Atlantic, on the contrary, with a well-established RFMO faced the critical challenge of limited fishing activities in the area, which was reflected in a relatively low interest from the EU operators involved in the project. The high-seas fisheries CS1 and CS2, were subject to a more qualitative and somewhat subjective audit, due to the nature of the OTs and the indicators set for them.

The Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) CSs on the other hand, reported more specific indicators towards improving knowledge and methods about the status of the different stocks. Focus was also placed on strengthening and increasing observer program coverage, with improved reporting methods and protocols, aiming to fully implement electronic reporting systems in the Coastal State with capacity to adequately process data from e-logbooks. Operators' compliance was also targeted through data analysis of satellite signals from remote sensing systems (VMS and AIS). Finally, socio-economic targets were set in this second version of the MRs, with focus on data collection for catches, landings, processing, and trade, as well as market analysis and other socio-economic variables.

The notable advancement from the MR1 to the MR2 showed extensive work that renders important results throughout the implementation of the RBM. For example, reports on the implementation of self-sampling programs for stock assessment, not only from the EU fleet but further, as in the case of Senegal involving artisanal fleet targeting the same species. In other cases, big data analysis was

conducted, adding evidence to the value of remote sensing as a tool for transparency and support compliance in fisheries activities (Ruiz et al., 2019). Furthermore, several protocols and documents were developed, which are ready for implementation by the coastal state authorities, such as the harmonized catch data protocol in Cape Verde, and self-sampling training materials and a specific protocol to improve on-board observations in Mauritania.

However, several challenges were also found in the implementation and performance of the MRs. Challenges with data collection due to existing data sharing restrictions, timing, and delays of planned actions, with the added challenge of a world pandemic, as well as issues with participation and active collaboration in the programs, were found in several cases. More notable for the four SFPA CSs, was the clear difference in the success of the actions where adequate coordination and collaboration was in place with the Coastal States.

The second audit process was conducted to the extent that the MRs were reported at the time of the audit. The second version of the MRs presented at this stage are not final, as work is still ongoing within the project. Therefore, this second audit is an intermediate revision of progress based on available results, limiting therefore the possibility to audit results from ongoing work not yet reported. Within the RBM, the audit framework allows for intermediate audits to assess performance every updated version of the MR, where frequency can be stipulated in the RBM contract. A final audit of the MRs should be planned within RBM to allow for the evaluation of all the actions taken and finalized within the framework. However, within FarFish, the final audit will not be possible due to time constraints and contractual specifications within the EU research and innovation action framework. Nevertheless, the implementation of this second audit framework should serve as a guideline to continue the evaluation of the future versions of the MRs developed within the RBM approach until their completion.

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Abbreviations and definitions

ACOPESCA	Competent Authority for Fishery Products, Cabo Verde
AIS	Automatic Identification System
AMP	Maritime and Port Agency, Cape Verde
ANFACO-CECOPESCA	National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures (Representing EU fishing and processing sector)
CAFS	Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences, governmental scientific institution of Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (MoA). The institution plays an influential role in Chinese national fisheries science and management policy.
CECAF	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries
CECAF-SC	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries Scientific Committee
CRODT	Centre de Recherche Océanographique de Dakar-Thiaroye
CS	Case Study
CSRP	Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission
CTMFM	Joint Argentinean-Uruguay Technical Commission of the Maritime Front (managing hake stock since 1975)
DARE	Directory of Fisheries Management in Mauritania
DFADs	Drifting Fish aggregating devices
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, EC
DGRM	General Directorate for Marine Resources, National Fisheries Authority, Cape Verde
DLM	Data Limited Method
DNEM	Directorate National of Maritime Economy, Cape Verde
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMS	Electronic monitoring system
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAD	Fish aggregating device
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FMC	Fisheries Monitoring Centre
FPAOI	The Federation of Artisanal Fishers of the Indian Ocean, Seychelles
FPA	Pelagic Freezer-trawler Association
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
ICES	International Exploration of the Sea
IEO	Instituto Español de Oceanografía
IMR	Institute of Marine Research
IMROP	Mauritanian Institute for Oceanographic Research and Fisheries (responsible for the approval of licenses and fishing vessels)
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estatística, Cape Verde
INIDEP	The National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development in Argentina
INPESCA	Cía Internacional de Pesca y Derivados, S.A., Seychelles
IOT	Indian Ocean Tuna, a branch of Union Thai
IOTC	The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
IOTC WGFADS	IOTC Working group on Fish aggregating devices
IRD	Institute for Research and Development
ISRA	Institut Sénégalais de Recherches Agricoles
ISSF	International seafood sustainability foundation
IUU	Illegal, unreported, and unregulated
LDAC	Long Distance Advisory council, EU fisheries body representing stakeholders of both fishing sector and other groups of interest
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MFMP	National Fisheries Management Plan

MFMR	Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources, Namibia
MPEM	Department of Fisheries and Maritime Economy, Mauritania
MPEM	Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy, Senegal
MSY	Maximum sustainable Yield
OPAGAC	Organisation of associated producers of large tuna freezer vessels, representing the purse seine fleet
OPROMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín, Spain
ORTHONGEL	French organisation of producers of frozen and deep-frozen tropical tuna
OT	Outcome Target
RBM	Results Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System
RSFP	Regional Fisheries Surveillance Project
SC SEAFO	Scientific Committee SEAFO
SEA	Southeast Atlantic
SEAFO	Southeast Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
SFA	Seychelles fishing Authority
SFPA	EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
SGP	Secretaría General de Pesca – Spanish FMC
SIOTI	The Sustainable Indian Ocean Tuna Initiative
SMSP	Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning
SWA	Southwest Atlantic
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WP	Work Package
WWF	Worldwide fund for nature
RBM	Results-Based Management
RBM-RFMS	RFMS is a fisheries management approach developed within the EcoFishMan project. The RFMS is an adaptive management system that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management.
OT	Outcome target (OT) is a specific and measurable performance goals defined for a fishery based on agreed and appropriately authorized general goals, standards, and principles, as defined by the authorities based on the policy objectives. The OT is the indicator value that the management actions aim to stay above or below e.g. $F < F_{msy}$
Authority	Organizational entity enacting authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission.
Operator	Organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management plans and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority

1 Introduction

The objective of WP5 is to evaluate the relevance, applicability, sustainability, costs, benefits, and compliance with the goals of the Management Recommendations (MR) developed by WP4 within the Results-Based Management (RBM) approach applied in the FarFish project. The RBM is a framework where a fisheries management authority may delegate specific management and documentation responsibilities to fisheries resource users (Nolde Nielsen et al., 2015). Within the RBM framework, the audit is a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MRs, including the monitoring and documentation measures, are being implemented as agreed.

This audit process builds on the framework developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (EcoFishMan, 2012b, 2014) and advances in the implementation of an audit process based on the actual application of the RBM model for the EU fisheries in international waters. In the FarFish project, the role of the auditor is to evaluate whether the contract between the authority (WP3) and the operator (WP4) has been fulfilled, in terms of the achievement of the outcome targets listed in the MR. The audit process within the framework of RBM in fisheries, evaluates the design and implementation of a Fisheries Management System, where:

“Defining an acceptable impact and leaving it to resource users to identify the means to meet the requirements and to document the effectiveness of the means, and ultimately achieve the requirements” (EcoFishMan, 2012a)

From this definition, the specification of acceptable impact (i.e. Outcome Targets¹), as well as the management means (i.e. indicators) are defined by the operators. The operators are then required to document the effectiveness of these management means, Outcome Targets are likely to be reached.

Hence, the audit process consists of two main stages, the first stage evaluates the implementation of the MR, where the auditor verifies that the documentation system defined by the operators and approved by the authority, satisfies the audit framework criteria in terms of quality of the data, evaluation of evidence and implementation. The first stage of the audit serves as a quality check of the MR, whilst the second stage will focus on its performance. During the second audit stage, the OTs will be evaluated by assessing the defined indicators, through three criteria, effectiveness performance,

¹ Specific and measurable performance goals defined for a fishery based on agreed and appropriately authorized general goals, standards, and principles, as defined by the authorities based on the policy objectives. In the case of a RBM, the outcome targets are found in policy documents. Since the exact formulation of the outcome targets depends on the infrastructure of the RBM system, outcome targets are not found in conventional management settings (EcoFishMan, 2012a)

compliance, and the effects of the management recommendations. In this stage of the audit, the indicators are evaluated as management means to reach the management goals or expected impacts of the OT. The second stage of the audit is then, a platform for the responsiveness of the MR, where the parts can take corrective steps and trigger management actions to respond to the needs of the fisheries within the RBM process.

The present document consists of the second and final audit process for the second version of the MR developed for six case studies (CS) within the project FarFish. Yet, it is worth clarifying that the second version of the MRs presented at this stage are not final, and it will continue to be developed as work is still ongoing within the project. Therefore, this audit is limited to the results presented in this version of the MRs. Within the RBM, the audit framework allows for intermediate audits that can be performed for every updated version of the MR, where frequency of the audit can be stipulated within the RBM contract. A final audit of the MRs should be conducted within the RBM framework, yet this will not be possible within the life of project. Nevertheless, this audit framework and process should serve as a guideline to continue the evaluation of the future versions of the MRs within the RBM framework and until their completion.

This second audit report is structured into three main sections, first the description of the audit framework and scoring system, followed by the audit of each of the six CS in FarFish, where each CS includes an update of the first audit on implementation and the second audit stage on performance. The combined results from these processes will be summarized in the final evaluation report or audit dashboard of each CS. The auditor team will draw some final recommendations to conclude the report.

2 Audit Framework: Evaluation of the Management Recommendations

To conduct the audit, the lead auditor in FarFish, represented by WP5, first formed an audit team for each of the CS, designating a group of three experts in fisheries management, biology and socioeconomics, from different organization within the FarFish consortium. Each audit team was assigned a case study (CS), which was audited following three formal checks. The first made by the primary auditor, later revised by two supporting auditors, and finally verified by the lead auditor, WP5 leader Blue Resource - Sjókovin.

As mentioned, the audit process builds on the framework developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (EcoFishMan, 2012b, 2014). This framework includes both ex-ante and ex-post evaluation of the MRs. The ex-ante evaluation was conducted in Deliverable 5.1 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2019), where the documentations system conformance in the MR1 for each CS (Mikkelsen et al., 2020) was audited. The second audit process will be based on the presented version of MR2 for each CS provided by WP4 in Deliverable 4.4, taking into account the “General Guidelines for making MRs” in deliverable D3.5 (Viðarsson et al., 2019), the second MR invitation submitted by WP3 in Deliverable 3.6 (Viðarsson et al., 2020), the report on challenges and suggestions for improvements in each CS in Deliverable 5.2 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2020). The focus of this second audit will be on changes, developments, and progress reported from the first to the second version of the MR. The audit framework will only evaluate reported actions to the extent they have been reported to be completed at this stage. Considering that this second MR of the MR is an intermediate version and work is still ongoing within the project, this audit is limited by this. An ex-post evaluation where the final audit of the completed version of the MR is performed, can only be done when the MR documents are final. According to this, the evaluation of management recommendation has been structured as follows:

2.1 Stage 1: Update of the audit of the implementation of the MR

The audit framework seeks to assess to what extent the MR developed by the Operator (WP4) is acceptable and likely to enable the Operator to achieve the outcome targets defined by the Authority (WP3). In the first stage of the audit, the auditor assesses whether the MR includes a precise assemble of reliable information applying adaptive management principles. To develop this task successfully, the audit is carried out as soon as the MRs have been approved. Hence, this audit stage is conducted for the first approved MR and followed-up every time the MR is revised or updated, and a new version has been approved by the authority.

The implementation audit is conducted in two sections, first the conformance of the documentation system and then performs a sensitivity analysis, combining a quantitative and qualitative analysis, where possible. These are to ensure that the MR includes a documentation system designed for

measuring the performance on relevant indicators (EcoFishMan, 2014). In this context, the auditor evaluates:

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

The first section of the audit is the documentation system conformance that builds on ensuring accurate documentation, detailing the minimum criteria for reliable data, and considering the cost-efficiency of the control system. This phase is organized in three subsequent steps explained² in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1 Steps to conduct the documentation system conformance assessment

The step 1 assesses the quality of the criteria for defining the indicators and documentation for the data necessary for accomplishing them. The OTs and indicators should comply with the SMART analysis, where the text of the OTs and the indicators should be Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Relevant and Timely. Step 2 evaluates evidence of availability of data necessary to meet with the selected indicators and, whether enough resources have been allocated across the different actors to implement the necessary actions and monitor them. Finally, step 3 assesses and describes the findings, providing recommendations to maintain the MR direction or adjust it.

These steps were done when the MR1 was audited in Deliverable 5.1 (FarFish, 2019). Now, they will be further evaluated in MR2, to verify adherence to the recommendations made by the auditor and hence, verifying that adequate information is flowing across the relevant parties to accomplish the goal of the OTs.

² See Review Audit Framework in Deliverable 5.1 (FarFish, 2019) for further details.

Considering that in fisheries management, there are clear constraints and boundaries (organisational, financial, technical, resources, capacity, etc.) that can only be resolved gradually over time, the RBM framework proposes to identify areas of responsibility, linked to transitional and stepwise implementation (EcoFishMan, 2014). In this RBM approach, the areas of responsibility, such as data collection, monitoring and control can be divided differently between operators, the authority, or external contracted agencies. The operator may choose to leave specific functions (e.g. data collection or control) to be carried out by e.g. the authority, in this way different functions of responsibility should be made clear in the MR.

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

The second section of the audit framework is a sensitivity analysis. Sensitivity analysis is an important component of the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)³, that involves changing parameters and the recalculation of the net present value of a project to identify the underlying uncertainty and convey how sensitive predicted impacts are to changes in assumptions. This type of analysis, serves as a tool for MRs that have set numerical limits and targets to change the key parameter of the fisheries management, such as fishing mortality, by-catch rates, landings, and discard levels, etc. For the RBM, these analyses are used to test whether changes in the selected key parameters lead to significant changes with regards to achieving the outcome targets for the MR. To conduct a sensitivity analysis, a baseline scenario must be established. A good baseline needs a strong factual basis and must be expressed in quantitative terms. It needs an appropriate time horizon (neither too long nor too short). The baseline projection shall provide a clear indication about the state of the current situation, to what extent it can worsen without intervention, and whether there are irreversible consequences already.

To conduct a sensitivity analysis, the MRs should have measurable socio-economic effects, so that a CBA analysis can be conducted. In some cases, this is not attainable due to difficulties to assign monetary value to some of the selected indicators in the different CSs. In the case of the MRs developed within FarFish, the Outcome Targets set between the authorities and operators, do not include numerical limits or targets with direct socio-economic effects for the selected fisheries. Most of the OTs defined in the six MRs are targeted towards improving ecological sustainability through data and capacity building, and adequate monitoring and control of the fisheries. Setting monetary values to these types of OTs is not possible. Only some OTs for selected CS include socioeconomic components, aiming to build knowledge on trade flow and obtain data to evaluate socioeconomic effects of specific fisheries. In those cases, data building is the main target, therefore a sensitivity analysis is not feasible. Due to these reasons, it was not possible to conduct the sensitivity analysis section for the MRs developed in FarFish.

³ Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a conceptual framework for the evaluation of the social desirability of a policy or project i to facilitate more efficient allocation of resources.

2.2 Stage 2: Audit and adaptation. Performance of MR

The second stage of the audit focuses on performance as a platform for the responsiveness, by providing useful information about key management points which should be revised and hence, trigger management actions. This RBM approach proposes that this audit stage is conducted periodically, so that the responsiveness of the management system is allowed. This audit stage should also be done to the final reporting of the MR, when all actions are considered finalized. The performance audit is broken down into three sections conducted as follows:

B. Performance Effectiveness audit

The Auditor should receive evidence about achievement (or not) of the OTs and demonstrate the success or failure to perform the management goals. The performance effectiveness audit is focused on measuring the results of the MR based on the selected indicators from the OTs. These indicators should be classified as biological, ecological, economic, social, and cultural according to the Management Recommendation Guidelines of the RBM. This phase is organized in three subsequent steps as shown in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2 Steps to audit Effectiveness Performance

Effectiveness performance will be evaluated for each of the indicators defined for the OTs accepted in the MR2, through the Effectiveness Ratios (ER) described in step 2. The ERs provide an estimation of the effectiveness of the implementation of the indicators and hence, report on the performance to accomplish the OT. This estimation will be based on the reported information of achievement for each of the indicators. The ER calculation serves to evaluate the performance of quantitative indicators but also can be adapted and implemented for qualitative indicators. When the indicators are quantitative, the MR should report the outcome of the implemented action. When the indicators are qualitative,

the auditor should set a numerical level of achievement according to the score system described in Table 3, by assessing which actions have been taken to accomplish the indicator. The assigned score level should be justified in text and supported in the actions reported in the MR.

C. Compliance Assessment

This stage of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendations. In the audit framework, this is measured through three components: Completeness, Timeliness and Source quality. These three components of compliance can be summarised as follows:

- **Completeness (C):** Evaluates to what degree the actions defined for the indicators (e.g. data requirements, analyses, documents, protocols, etc) for each of the approved OTs have been collected and performed.
- **Timeliness (T):** Evaluates to what degree the actions to achieve the indicators have been performed on-time and at the frequency specified in the MR (e.g. once, annually or at other intervals).
- **Source quality (S):** Evaluates to what degree the actions to achieve the OTs have been performed by the relevant bodies specified in the MR.

As a result of these three analyses, a compliance index will be calculated and reported using the traffic light method (Caddy, 2017) to inform both authority and operators about the compliance’s state of the reported data (including gaps, limitations, etc.). The assessment can be graphically depicted in the following three steps in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Steps to audit compliance and estimate compliance index

The three components of the analysis are evaluated in step 1. A numerical level from 0 to 5 should be assigned to each of the components based on the reported information provided in the MR. The three components are summarized through the compliance index (C.I) described in step 2, and further elaborated as follows:

Compliance Index (C.I): Verifies that criteria of indicators are met as direct result of implemented actions. Done through a quantitative analysis, including the three components described in Table 1:

Table 1 Components and definitions of the compliance index (C.I)

Compliance Index C.I.	
Component	Definition
Completeness (C)	Completed actions required to accomplish goal
Timeliness (T)	Requirements presented on time and according to frequency defined
Source quality (S)	Requirements presented by relevant body

$$C.I. = \left(\frac{C + T + S}{3} \right)$$

The analysis verifies that the Operators (WP4) provided sufficient documentation, which is robust and acceptable according to the three compliance parameters. The auditor will assess this, according to the information presented in the MR, and assigned a score level according to the scoring system presented in Table 3.

A summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (C.I.) that will be reported in the audit dashboard. This index will inform both Authority and Operators about the state of the reported data with regards to compliance.

D. Management Recommendation Effects in socioeconomic terms

In this third and final phase, the auditor will conduct an evaluation on the potential effects of the MRs to determine potential positive and negative consequences of the implementation of the recommended actions, described in the management recommendations as Outcome Targets (OT).

Strengths and weaknesses of potential alternatives are most often assessed in formal cost-benefit analysis (CBA) which seeks to calculate the present value of the cost and income (benefits) streams of the relevant alternatives, and thus analyse if the action to be taken is beneficial to the society as a whole, rather than to certain groups or stakeholders (e.g. individuals, firms or governments). CBA may be used both to determine if an investment/decision is financially sound, i.e. if the benefits outweigh the costs, and for ranking the options at hand.

A full-blown CBA may be conducted in cases where all costs and benefits can be assessed in monetary terms, but a partial CBA may be employed when some of the costs and benefits, i.e. social and environmental impacts, are non-monetary (Blaha & Lefeuvre, 2017).

Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) may also be employed if it is inappropriate to place monetary values on some of the benefits, such as health outcomes. Rather than examine all the costs and benefits of a certain action, CEA seeks to determine the relative costs of pursuing different policies that all have a similar outcome. Nevertheless, Cost-effectiveness analysis is closely related to cost-benefit analysis in that both represent economic evaluations of alternative resource use and measure costs in the same way (Levin, 1995).

Both CBA and CEA assume that information on at least the most important costs can be obtained, with CBA also requiring data on some of the benefits. However, in some cases the costs and/or benefits associated with pursuing a certain action may not be clear or unavailable. In such cases, a more basic approach may be followed by first classifying the impacts (for instance, financial, institutional, managerial, environmental, political) and then simply outlining the size (small, medium, large) and temporal nature (short-run, medium-run, long-run) of the expected costs and benefits and the impact they can be expected to have on individual stakeholders.

The OTs defined and reported in the MRs for the six CS in the FarFish project, are mostly related to qualitative aspects of the fisheries management and do not have any clearly defined associated costs and benefits. Traditional CBA or CEA can therefore not be conducted. Instead, the OTs are assessed using the more basic approach outlined above and described further in Table 2.

Table 2 Steps to evaluating Management Effect of the MR

Steps	Considerations
1. <i>Identify the potential impacts of the OT</i>	Consider the goal OT and which areas of the fisheries can be impacted by implementing this action, compared to not taking any action (business as usual)
2. <i>Define whether the impact represents a cost or a benefit</i>	Define whether the impact will incur costs or whether it will yield benefits
3. <i>Define scale of impact</i>	Consider the potential scale of the impact. Low, medium, or high and justify in text
4. <i>Identify which group of stakeholders will be affected</i>	Assess which groups of stakeholders will bear the costs and/or receive the benefits of the actions
5. <i>Define the temporal nature of the impact</i>	Estimate when will the impact of the action most likely occur and for how long the expected impacts are likely to last
6. <i>Report</i>	According to the previous step, analyse, report, and prepare recommendations, if necessary.

2.3 MR Evaluation: Scoring and audit summary

The scoring system allows the audit team to scrutinize Outcome Targets (OTs) of diverse nature, allowing for both quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the progress reports provided in the Management Recommendations. The auditor evaluates the MRs through the audit framework and then, assigns a level of audit achievement described in Table 3. At this stage, it is important to highlight, that the achievement level in the audit does not necessarily correspond to the achievement reported in the Management Recommendations, as the auditor evaluates this level according to the audit framework only.

Table 3 Scoring system and traffic light to report on the audit results per criteria

Percentage achieved	Score	TL Colour	Audit achievement Level
100%	5		Finalized
75%	4		High achievement. Few actions required to full achievement
50%	3		Medium. Some relevant actions are still pending
25%	2		Low achievement. Several important actions are still pending or not reported.
0%	1		Not actions reported or fundamental data is not available.
NA			Not evaluated /Unknown

Each of the OTs reported in the MRs, both obligatory and recommended will be scored individually. Depending on the stage of the audit, the OT can be evaluated at the indicator level. The audit summary will be presented through an “audit dashboard” that displays the audit results on the implementation and performance of the MR to the point where it is being audited. This dashboard aims to serve as an operational tool which provides feedback to both Authority and Operator. An illustration of the “Audit dashboard” can be seen in Figure 4.

	PHASE		OT 1	OT 2	OT 3
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1		N/A	
	Documentation system	Crit. 2			
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant			
Responsive Assessment					
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER			
	Compliance Assessment	CI		N/A	
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			On-going	Finalized	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment				
	Final assessment				

Figure 4 Illustrative Example of the audit dashboard

The audit dashboard should be utilized as a tool to continue developing the MRs utilising the RBM principles to draw attention to the areas that need more efforts to either redirect the target or dedicate additional efforts and resources towards accomplishing it. The audit dashboard is the final statement of the auditor and should be provided in every intermediate audit and in the final ex-post evaluation.

3 CS1: High seas: South-West Atlantic fisheries

3.1 General remarks

The Management Recommendations (MR2) for SWA fisheries (FAO area 41) was submitted on February 22nd, 2021. The audit process is thereafter initiated.

The MR2 is a follow up report of performance from MR1 proposed for the international mixed fishery in FAO Area 41, in the subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2, at the part of the Patagonian shelf and slope (< 300 m) that extends beyond the Argentina EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone. This area does not have a Regional Fisheries Organization acting as a key body responsible for managing fisheries. This makes the coexistence of international fleets within the area difficult. Especially due to the little to no dialogue or exchange of information between the different fishing nations/authorities operating in this area, due to the unresolved controversy with Falkland-Malvinas FPZ between Argentina and United Kingdom. This long-standing issue constitutes a main challenge in terms of fisheries governance in an area with different levels of regulation and monitoring, control, and surveillance (MCS) of the various flag states, and a lack of a shared scientific knowledge base for the regulation of targeted species.

3.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendation

A. Stage 1: Analysis of the MR Implementation

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. To conduct this task successfully, an audit of the management recommendations is carried out. This stage is broken down into two phases: a documentation system conformance analysis (A.1), and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 CS1: Documentation System Conformance

For MR2, the documentation system conformance is audited based on the results from the first audit of MR1 (FarFish, 2019) and further, an assessment of whether there have been any changes (positive or negative), based on evidence from MR2.

AUTHORITIES

There is no competent regional or national fisheries management authority to take the lead in the RBM process. In the FarFish project, WP3 representatives from MATIS have acted as the leading authority. The auditor considers that the representative of the authority is clearly stated in MR2. The role of other authorities mentioned (FAO, DG Mare, coastal states and flag states) is that of consulting authorities,

however the absence of a fisheries management organization remains a challenge for adequate representation.

OPERATOR

MR2 states that the European fishing operators qualified to respond to the MR Invitation will provide feedback through the EU Long Distance Fleet Advisory Council (LDAC). LDAC drafted MR2 in collaboration with FarFish project partner CETMAR. WP4 led by UiT acts as the operators' representative within the project.

The MR1 audit recommended that a list of implicated vessels was presented. This has not been provided for MR2. However, in subsequent sections, statements of active participation and interaction between stakeholders, suggests that actions have been taken to promote involvement from operators.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

In MR2 the main goal is to improve the sustainability of the high-seas fisheries in the Southwest Atlantic (SWA), this is stated in Section 1.5. The relevance of the items in the numbered list following the main goal are not clearly stated, but the auditor interprets these as narrowing and further specifying the main goal. The MR1 audit recommended to link these goals to challenges of the fisheries in this area. MR2 provides background for defining these objectives in separate sections on the legal framework, stock status and specific challenges of the SWA high-seas fisheries. The auditor considers that this satisfies the recommendation.

OUTCOME TARGETS AND INDICATORS

Based on the revision of indicators and strategies in the MR2 for the SWA fisheries, an update of the implementation audit is conducted. The auditor also evaluates whether actions have been taken towards resolving the issues found in the first audit.

A summary of the OTs and indicators defined for the CS of the SWA fisheries, indicating the management objectives they relate to, is presented in Table 4 below. The OTs were changed from MR1, some with minor changes to wording (OT 1.1-1.3), others were more fundamentally changed (OT 1.3). One (O.T 1.4) on Both EU and non-EU fleet VMEs protection in accordance with UNGA 61/105 and FAO Guidelines for Management of Deep-Sea Waters in the high seas was dropped from MR1 to MR2, on the grounds of closure of several areas where restrictions apply solely to the EU fleet, which according to MR2, requires additional efforts for a collaborative approach to find consensus on the need to protect VMEs. So instead of defining a specific OT for this purpose, focus will be given to OT 1.1. as it partly addresses this need.

Table 4 Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators of CS SWA

Management Objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Contribute to a level playing field for international fleets involved in the sustainable fisheries in the SWA fisheries	OT 1.1 A soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) available (Obligatory)	I_1_CS1: Number of invited stakeholders attending the Conference - Indicator cat: A I_2_CS1: Verify that International Conference has been held - Indicator cat: C I_3_CS1: Report from the conference delivered - Indicator cat: C I_4_CS1: Embed the conference in the current International Ocean Governance Agenda of the European Commission - Indicator cat: C
Contribute to improved fishing and conservation through monitoring, control and surveillance mechanisms	OT 1.2 All vessels transmit AIS signals (Obligatory)	I_5_CS1: Verify operator compliance - Indicator cat: B
	OT 1.3 Theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO41 as a basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region (Recommended)	I_6_CS1: Pilot project launched - Indicator cat: C

OT 1.1 A soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) available

OT 1.1 has been redefined from a soft-law mechanism to be developed to being available. This improves the measurability of the OT. The auditor considers that OT 1.1 along with the selected indicators continue to be acceptable according to the SMART principles. The auditors' comments on including an additional indicator to verify the conference proceeding was adequately taken upon with indicator I_3_CS1. Regarding I_4_CS1 about the possibility to embed the conference in the current International Ocean Governance Agenda of the European Commission, this indicator was defined to ensure continuity of the action, yet the auditors consider that the next steps for a future continuation of the dialogue have not been fully described. The additional indicators included, which answer to the first audit recommendations, are considered by the auditors to be an acceptable action within the framework of the FarFish project.

Risks towards not achieving OT1.1. are described in the progress section 5.3.2 of the MR2. The auditor considers that adequate actions have been taken to mitigate them. As stated in MR2, the Covid-19

pandemic required a change of approach for the implementation of this OT. The potential lack of participation due to associated travel restrictions was adequately tackled by organizing the Conference online. The next major risk reported to implementing the strategy, refers to ensuring the continuity of this strategy. For this purpose, adequately documenting the actions towards achieving indicator I_4_CS1 is of particular importance.

OT 1.2 All vessels transmitting AIS signals

OT 1.2 has been redefined as “All vessels transmitting AIS signals”, removing VMS due to lack of availability from all fleets. The indicator I_5_CS1 associated to this OT has been also redefined from “operator compliance” to “verify operator compliance”, measured with category B. The MR1 audit had no specific comments to the previous version of this OT, apart from the indicator category applied and requesting revising the SMART⁴ formulation of the OT. The rephrasing of the indicator and changed category are improved and more correlated to action. Yet, the link between the specified key activity “developing a big-data analysis of AIS and VIIRS-DNB” and the OT is not clear. The key activity relates to the objective, but the OT itself relates to the information necessary to carry out the activity. The auditor suggests adjusting the text of the OT, to better reflect the target of verifying through remote sensing the transmission of AIS signals from all vessels in the SWA area. Still, the auditor team considers that the OT and the key activity are achievable and contribute towards the specified management objective.

OT 1.3 Theoretical frame for a specific control and inspection programme in FAO41 as a basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region

OT 1.3 has been redefined and this answers partly to the SMART issues raised in audit 1. The OT has been changed from obligatory to recommended. Nevertheless, MR2 defines a clear action plan for the implementation of this OT, with clear statements of assignability and relevance of the task, which indicates that sufficient documented actions have been taken towards achieving this OT. Along with the key activity and the specified indicators, the OT is considered adequate.

⁴ The SMART acronym stands for Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Relevant and Timely

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been any OTs with direct socio-economic implications formulated in the MR2 for SWA no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis. Therefore, this analysis will not be conducted.

B. Summary of Documentation System Conformance

To finalize this first stage of audit, the criteria for the evaluation of the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 5. These results will be also included in the audit dashboard in Table 13, together with the results of the second stage of the audit performance.

Table 5 CS1 Southwest Atlantic: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

Outcome Target	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program	
	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 1.1 A soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) available	The organization and plans for arranging a conference have been briefly described in the MR2.			
OT 1.2 All vessels transmitting AIS signals	The methodology and collected data are not described in MR2, but in a separate report. The data and analyses performed by CSIC allows for assessment of the AIS and remote sensing data and hence contribute to the selected indicator.			
OT 1.3 Theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO41 as basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region	This OT is largely based in the results from the international conference reported in OT1.1. Relevant stakeholders have been consulted about their willingness to participate, and a structure of the concept document is presented in MR2. The concept note is provided and pending validation.			

C. Stage 2: MR performance audit and adaptation for CS1

This RBM framework proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for such responsiveness. There are two phases to support this stage, effectiveness, and compliance evaluation.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

OT 1.1 *A soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) available*

To verify the performance of OT 1.1, the operator has agreed upon four indicators as shown in Table 4. A progress report is presented in section 5.3.1 of the MR2, where in the summary table states that the indicators are not ready to be evaluated. However, after the completion of MR2, the auditors verified that an international conference was held on the March 4th, 2021, with over 100 stakeholders participating. A report from the meeting is in preparation. Table 6 reports the auditors' evaluation for each of the indicators selected for OT1.1.

Table 6 Effectiveness performance of the selected indicators for OT 1.1

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_1_CS1: <i>Number of invited stakeholders attending the Conference.</i> - Indicator cat: A	Relevant activities have been done to accomplish this indicator. The auditors have been informed through communication from the organizers, that 192 people registered and 144 participated in some parts of the conference, with about 100 participants following the whole event. The auditors consider this a high attendance and warrants a high score.	5
I_2_CS1: <i>Verify that International Conference has been held.</i> - Indicator cat: C	The auditors are informed that the conference was held. A group of this auditor team attended the conference. The official report of results is pending to finalize the OT.	4
I_3_CS1: <i>Report from the conference delivered.</i> - Indicator cat: C	At the time of the MR writing, the report has not been delivered. However, as the conference was recently held during the time of the audit, the auditors assume that this indicator is on track to be achieved and that there is low risk to not achieving it. Further, the auditors have received information that the report was submitted 26 th of March. This should be reported in the next version of the MR to finalize the indicator achievement.	4

I_4_CS1: Embed the conference in the current International Ocean Governance Agenda of the European Commission - Indicator cat: C	This indicator is dependent on the international conference participation, discussions, and outcomes. All these factors include uncertainties that cannot be estimated at this point. A medium risk level is assigned. Conference participants have indicated willingness to continue scientific collaboration.	3
ER Score		4

OT 1.2 All vessels transmitting AIS signals

In the MR2, only one indicator was defined for OT 1.2, as presented in Table 4. The indicator I_5_CS1 aims to verify the operator compliance with the transmission of AIS signals. The indicator is to be confirmed through the development of a big-data analysis conducted by FarFish partner CSIC (Ruiz et al., 2019), combining two independent sources of information, namely AIS and VIIRS-DNB, to measure the degree of consistency of remote sensing. Table 7 presents the evaluation of the effectiveness in performing the necessary activities to achieve this indicator.

Table 7 Effectiveness of the selected indicators performance of OT 1.2

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_5_CS1: Verify operator compliance. - Indicator cat: B	MR2 reports that a big-data analysis has been published by CSIC (Ruiz et al., 2019). The results evidence significant correlation of two independent data sources. The OT achieved the desired impacts, by demonstrating that remote sensing adds transparency to the fishing operations in high seas where enforcement is challenging.	5
ER Score		5

OT 1.3 Theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO41 as basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region

Two indicators were defined for evaluating OT 1.3. First, I_6_CS1 referring to the development of a proposal for the pilot project and second, I_7_CS1 on the launching of the pilot project. For I_6_CS1, MR2 reports that the proposal is under development and, that it will be ready for validation early 2021. The final proposal is expected to be ready by the end of 2021, which is passed the project's end. MR2 reports important stakeholder interaction and feedback. Considering that this OT is highly dependent on the results from the international Conference (OT1.1), that was recently held, the auditor finds that this dependence explains the status of the action, and highlights that several important steps are still pending for achieving the target. The auditor remarks the need to ensure that all actions taken towards achieving I_7_CS1 should be followed up even after the lifetime of the FarFish project.

Table 8 Effectiveness of the selected indicators performance of OT 1.3

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_6_CS1: Proposal for a pilot project developed. - Indicator cat: C	An outline for a proposal is described in MR2. MR2 states that this will be ready by end of 2021. As the document is not yet ready for validation, the auditor considers that although low risk of not achieving this OT is assigned, some important actions are still pending, which implies an ER score of 3.	3
I_7_CS1: Pilot project launched. - Indicator cat: C	MR2 states that it is unlikely that this indicator will be achieved during FarFish timeline due to the political challenges ongoing in the area. The project must ensure that the proposal is validated and transmitted to the relevant entities in due time, and follow up on this action, even after the project is finished.	2
ER Score		2,5

C.2 Compliance

This item of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. In the described audit framework, this is measured through three levels - completeness, timeliness, and source quality. The compliance assessment determines the level for each of the three components for each OT. The summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (C.I.) that will be reported in the audit dashboard.

OT 1.1 *A soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) available*

The compliance assessment results for OT 1.1. are presented in Table 9 for each of the three components. These are evaluated according to what is reported in MR2. However, the auditor team may consider information made available during the audit process, even if not yet reported in MR2. This should be clearly stated in the audit report.

Table 9 Assessment of three parameters of the compliance audit for OT1.1.

Level	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness(C)	The MR2 indirectly specifies that data on participation, the conference being held, and a report being prepared are the relevant data for measuring completeness. Although not yet published, there was high participation rate, and the conference was held. A report is not yet available. Although subjectively set, this warrants a score of 4 (Scale 1-5) for the Completeness Level.	4
Timeliness (T)	The MR2 did not specify timing of the conference but was supposed a one-off event in the FarFish lifetime. It indicates that a goal is to embed in the International Ocean Governance agenda for the European Commission, but this has not been reported being achieved yet.	3
Source quality (S)	MR2 does not specify data sources for the indicators, but this is of little relevance. No score is assigned.	N/A
Total CI Score		3,5

OT 1.2 All vessels transmitting AIS signals

For the OT 1.2, the compliance assessment is presented in Table 10, where three parameters are described. The auditor also assigned scores for each of them and reports on the final compliance index.

Table 10 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT1.2.

Level	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness (C)	Data are specified to come from both Global Fishing Watch and Google Earth Engine. Both are collected and used in the CSIC study. Hence C scores 5.	5
Timeliness (T)	The MR2 did not specify timing of the conference but was supposed a be completed in the FarFish lifetime. Hence T scores 5.	5
Source quality (S)	Data are obtained from the specified sources. Hence S scores 5.	5
Total CI Score		5

OT 1.3 Theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO41 as basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region

For OT 1.3 the compliance assessment is presented in Table 11. For this OT, the auditor team reports concern on the timeliness of the action, acknowledging the dependence of this OT to the International Conference results recently held. The auditor further acknowledges that the implementation of the pilot project faces several challenges due to the unresolved controversy about Falkland-Malvinas FPZ

between Argentina and UK. Nevertheless, the auditors remark the need to ensure that this action is followed up even after the lifetime of the FarFish project, to ensure that resources employed to develop and validate this pilot project are well utilized.

Table 11 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT1.3.

Level	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness (C)	A concept note is under development to be validated. Important steps are yet to be taken. Commitment and involvement from relevant entities is necessary.	3
Timeliness (T)	The concept note is expected to be done early 2021 and be thereafter validated. However, the project is expected to be launched by the end of 2021. The FarFish project must ensure that the action is continued after the lifetime of the project.	2
Source quality (S)	The concept structure was developed considering the methodology and structure for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme (SCIP) developed by the European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA), who is also a member of the FarFish Reference Group. Relevant stakeholders were consulted, as well as control authorities and experts were consulted as reported in section 5.5.2. Relevant steps for validation are pending and commitment from reference group need to be ensured.	3
Total CI Score		2,7

D. MR Effects

This item of the audit aims to evaluate the impact of the MR in monetary terms. As the available framework documents available to us are not clear, we have interpreted this to the best of our abilities. Ideally, a cost-benefit analysis of the MR should have been performed. However, data are often limited and uncertain, as well as the impacts of management measures being difficult to ascertain and isolate from other factors. The MRs for the selected case studies are also not aimed at managing the fisheries, but rather focus on very limited areas within the fisheries and its management. Both the costs and benefits arising from the actions associated with each of the outcome targets are to a very little extent studied within the project. In the case of the SWA there is no OTs relevant for a quantitative cost-benefit analysis. Thus, we have resorted to a qualitative assessment of the OTs and associated activities.

OT 1.1 *Soft-law mechanism focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO area 41) available*

On a general basis hosting and attending a regular conference impose some costs, although quite modest. The benefits from these measures are difficult to ascertain, but there may be positive long-term impacts on the yield of the fisheries and improved management may provide considerable economic benefits. These benefits may primarily be gained by vessel owners, but society would benefit from trickle down effects, as well as higher consumer surplus. The public can also gain depending on how access to resources is granted – several mechanisms may be employed to reallocate part of the benefit from vessels to society. Achieving agreements around the utilization of these resources may also allow for reduced fishing capacity being employed. This has shorter-term benefits that would be gained primarily by vessel owners. Table 12 presents the analysis of the MR effects in terms of potential costs and benefits, according to the methodology described in the audit framework section, summarized in Table 2

Table 12 *Analysis of potential costs and benefits from OT1.1.*

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Direct costs associated	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Improved yield from fisheries	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners and trickle effects to society	Long
Reduced capacity employed	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners	Short-medium and long

OT 1.2 *All vessels transmitting AIS signals*

The conducted big-data analysis of AIS data is already incurred. The costs are very modest in relation to the value added from the fishery. The analysis performed revealed that remote sensing can be a useful tool in monitoring of the fishery. The benefits achieved so far beyond this knowledge improvement are likely very modest. However, this may be utilized in future management and control and allow for the same benefits and distribution as described for OT 1.1.

OT 1.3 *Frame for control and inspection programme*

Creating a pilot control and inspection programme would imply costs for the states involved, however the likelihood of being implemented is highly uncertain and cost allocation between states, vessels and other parties is uncertain.

3.3 Summary of the Audit

The audit dashboard for the CS1 in FarFish is presented in Table 13. The audit dashboard summarizes of the audit scores for the second version of the MR presented for the Southwest Atlantic high sea’s fisheries. Overall, the OT and indicators selected for this CS1 have been performing well for the purposes of the CS. Although some actions are pending, the contract between the authority and the organization is likely to be fulfilled. Important attention should be taken to ensure continuity for achieving OT 1.3 even after the project’s end.

Table 13 Audit dashboard: Summary of evaluation of CS1 Southwest Atlantic MR2

	PHASE		OT 1.1	OT 1.2	OT 1.3
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1			
	Documentation system	Crit. 2			
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant			
Responsive Assessment					
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER			
	Compliance Assessment	CI			
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			On-going	Finalized	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment				
	Final assessment				

4 CS2: High seas: South-East Atlantic fisheries

4.1 General remarks

The final Management Recommendations (MR2) for fisheries in the SEAFO Convention area (FAO area 47) was submitted on February 24th, 2021. The audit process was then initiated.

MR2 is a follow up report of performance from MR1 which was proposed for the fishery in the SEAFO Convention area (CA). The SEAFO Convention area is covered by the high seas area beyond the EEZ of Angola, Namibia, South Africa and the United Kingdom on behalf of St. Helena and its dependencies of Tristan de Cunha and Ascension Island. The contracting parties to SEAFO are Angola, the EU, Japan, Namibia, Norway, South Africa and South Korea. As stated in the second MR invitation presented by the authority representative in Deliverable 3.6 (Viðarsson et al., 2020), very limited fishing activity is conducted in waters beyond areas of national jurisdiction within the FAO Area 47 (under the jurisdiction of SEAFO). Most of the area is deep sea (>2000 m) with some seamounts, where limited fisheries are taking place. This limited fishing activity is mostly conducted within two subareas B1 and D1. Only two Spanish vessels have showed some activity in 2017, but no catches were reported. Other fleets operating in the SEAFO CA in that same year were Japan and Namibia.

The Outcome Targets (OTs) identified in the Second MR invitation in D3.6 are stated to be on a more “theoretical” level and the MR2 serves as a guideline. The relatively new RFMO, combined with the low fishing effort in the area, makes this a good case to demonstrate good practice recommendations. The actors involved in the RBM process therefore remain the same: MATIS (task leaders D3.6) acts as the leading authority within RBM, whilst considering input from the relevant authorities, e.g. SEAFO, DG MARE. UiT (WP4) acts as operators, with involvement from the task contributors, NOFIMA, IMR, and UCAM. The audit will be conducted by WP5 leader Sjókovin - Blue Resource.

4.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendations (MR)

A. MR Implementation audit

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. An update of the implementation audit of the management recommendations is carried out. This stage is broken down in two phases: documentation system conformance analysis (A.1) and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

For MR2, the documentation system conformance is audited based on the results from the first audit of MR1 in D5.1, the roadmap on opportunities and challenges in D5.2 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2019, 2020) and following the evolution of the MR invitation and MR approval between the operators and authorities (Deliverable 3.6 and 4.4). Furthermore, an assessment has been conducted of whether there are any changes (positive or negative) based on evidence from MR2.

AUTHORITIES

MR2 for the Southeast Atlantic (SEA) high seas fisheries states that the authorities are represented by WP3 led by Matís, with input from the operating RFMO for this area, the Southeast Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO), also from DG MARE relevant for the EU and final, relevant coastal states. No changes are reported since MR1.

OPERATOR

As stated, there is limited fishing activity in the Southeast Atlantic (SEA) high seas which creates little incentive for operators to participate in the RBM process. The operators for this area are represented by WP4 led by the Arctic University of Norway, with contribution of task leaders NOFIMA, IMR and UCAM. No active EU vessels or any relevant association are involved. MR2 states that the report is a theoretical exercise, to be considered in the event of increasing fishing activity in the area.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

The MR1 document (Mikkelsen et al., 2020) stated that the goal of the RBM process will serve as good practice recommendation with focus on improving monitoring for sustainable fisheries and support the maintenance of the international framework operated by SEAFO. In MR2 specific objectives were stated as follows:

- 1) Improve data quality and quantity.
- 2) Advance biological knowledge in the SEAFO area.
- 3) Contribute to better monitoring in the area by supporting enforcement through the utilization of the latest available satellite systems and tools

These objectives are in line with the specific challenges of the area described in section 4 of the MR2 document, and with the outcome targets set in section 5.

OUTCOME TARGETS AND INDICATORS

Based on the revision of indicators and strategies in the MR2 for the SEA high seas fisheries, a new audit is conducted. The auditor also evaluates whether actions have been taken towards resolving the issues found in the first audit.

A summary of the OTs and indicators defined for the CS of the SEA fisheries, indicating the management objectives they relate to, is presented in Table 14 below. There were no changes of the OTs from MR1, some only minor changes to wording.

Table 14 Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators of CS2 SEA

Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Improve knowledge base for sustainable fisheries management	OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks. Obligatory	I_1_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between MFMR and SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country - Indicator category: C I_2_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e-logbooks - Indicator category: C
Contribute to improved fishing and conservation through monitoring, control and surveillance mechanisms	OT 2.2 All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals. Obligatory	I_3_CS2: The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geolocation - Indicator category: B I_4_CS2: The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS + VMS) geolocation - Indicator category: A
	OT 2.3 All vessels have onboard observers. Recommended	I_5_CS2: Training of observers and observers available - Indicator category: C

For the OT2.1, the indicators were reorganized and reworded compared to MR1. In terms of the SMART analysis, the indicator I_1_CS2 which refers to “Initiate a dialogue meeting between MFMR and SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country” was made more specific and assignable by specifying one relevant contracting party, this satisfies the recommendation made in the first audit. The auditor considers the link between the OT2.1 and the indicators to be relatively weak, considering that the target is for all catches to be reported via E-logbooks. Suggested indicators for this OT could be, for example, increase in the number of vessels reporting via e-logbooks or percentage of catches reported through such systems. Furthermore, the relevance of the OT2.1 and its indicators to the management issues in the area remains unclear, as stated in the MR1 audit. MR2 reports first that SEAFO already uses an electronic reporting system and second, that the SEAFO Scientific Committee considered implementing a new electronic system is of little benefit. In that light, indicator I_2_CS2 on developing a pilot project to introduce e-logbook is also questioned in terms of relevance, as the costs of developing this project are considered by the relevant authorities of little benefit.

OT2.2. was rephrased from “Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals” to “All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals”. This contributes to measurability and assignability of the OT, following the SMART

analysis performed in MR1 audit. The links between OT2.2 for all vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals and the selected indicators are good. Yet, the measurability of the OT is questioned as it was assumed in MR1 that EU vessels were transmitting VMS data. Yet, MR2 reports that SEAFO has no VMS data for the EU-fleet. According to MR2, other sources such as Global Fishing watch (GFW) report activity of EU vessels in the area from 2015 to 2018, although they appear to be targeting migratory species that are out of the scope of SEAFO. The relevance of the indicator and OT is therefore questioned when no fishing activity from the EU fleet is reported in this area.

OT2.3 was defined as “All vessels have onboard observers” compared to MR1 where it was defined as “Onboard observers”. This OT was not developed in MR1 therefore it was not audited. Rewording the OT has made it more specific and measurable. The defined indicator I_5_CS2 on “Training of observers and observers available” refers to the key activity of capacity building and to the availability of observers, as it is specified in the section 5.5 of the MR2. However, the relevance and assignability of the OT and the defined indicator I_5_CS2 is questioned as no fishing activity from the EU-fleet is reported in this area. The SMART analysis will be performed for this indicator in Table 15.

Table 15 SMART analyses for I_5_CS2

Specific	Partly, the indicator is connected to the OT in terms of capacity building, not to the implementation of the action.
Measurable	No, the indicator does not provide any quantitative indication e.g. Number of available observers for training
Assignable	Partly, the entities in charge of the task are not stated. The auditor assumed from MR2 that is SEAFO
Relevant	Partly, due to the theoretical exercise of the CS, but questioned due to lack of fishing activity of the EU fleet
Time	No, does not state a timeline or deadline

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated any OT with direct socio-economic implications in the MR2 for SEA, no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis. This analysis will therefore not be performed.

B. Summary Documentation System Conformance Audit

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 16 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 23

Table 16 CS2 Southeast Atlantic: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

Outcome Target	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.	
	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks (obligatory)	Data of the SEAFO ERS (Electronic Reporting System) requirements have been collected, and the proposal was presented to the SEAFO Scientific Committee.			
OT 2.2 All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals (obligatory)	Methodology is not described in MR2. Data were sought from SEAFO and GFW, but the former had no data and FarFish were not able to analyse the latter data.			
OT 2.3 All vessels have onboard observers (recommended)	FarFish did not pursue the implementation of a training program, as operators were not interested in this action due to lack of fishing activity. Nevertheless, SEAFO can conduct training programs that will satisfy the need of the EU fleet if fisheries resume.			

C. MR Audit and adaptation

The RBM proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for such responsiveness. There are two phases to support this stage, effectiveness performance and compliance evaluation.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks. **Obligatory**

To verify the performance of OT 2.1, the operator has agreed upon two indicators as shown in Table 14. A progress report is presented in section 5.3 of the MR2 of the CS2, where it outlines the communication/dialogue with SEAFO on the development of a pilot study. As there is no fishing activity by the EU fleet in the area, and an ERS system is already in place, the SEAFO SC agreed that this will not be implemented. No further action will be taken on this OT. Table 17 presents the evaluation of effectiveness performance for the two defined indicators in OT 2.1, and the ER score assigned.

Table 17 Effectiveness performance evaluation of the selected indicators in OT 2.1.

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_1_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country Indicator category: C	Relevant action has been taken to accomplish this indicator. Although a dialogue between SEAFO and Namibia has not been initiated, it has addressed the SEAFO Scientific Committee.	5
I_2_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e-logbooks Indicator category: C	The SEAFO did not see the need for developing a pilot project in a situation with no fisheries. It however acknowledged that such a project could enhance data integrity and quality in a situation where fishing was taking place.	1
ER score		3

OT 2.2 All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals. **Obligatory**

To verify the performance of OT2.2, the operator has agreed upon two indicators as shown in Table 14. A progress report is presented in section 5.4 of the MR2, where it is stated that it is not able to conduct the big-data analysis due to lack of data. The reason is that there is no VMS data for EU vessels

in the SEAFO system, and that the AIS data from Global Fishing Watch is not detailed enough. The OT will therefore not be achieved. The performance evaluation is presented in Table 18.

Table 18 Effectiveness performance evaluation of the selected indicators in OT 2.2.

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_3_CS2: The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geolocation Indicator category: B	Relevant actions were taken to get access to the data. There are however no VMS data for EU vessels in the SEAFO system	2
I_4_CS2: The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS + VMS) geolocation Indicator category: A	No VMS data was available from SEAFO and the GFW data was inaccessible. Thus, analysis was not performed	1
ER score		1,5

OT 2.3 All vessels have onboard observers. Recommended

To verify the performance of OT2.3, the operator has agreed upon one indicator as shown in Table 14. A progress report is presented in section 5.5 of the MR2, where it is stated that no operators are willing to put in the effort of training observers due to no fishing activity in the area. The OT will therefore not be achieved and is considered finalized. The performance evaluation is presented in Table 19.

Table 19 Effectiveness performance evaluation of the selected indicators in OT 2.3

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_5_CS2: Training of observers and observers available Indicator score: C	Relevant actions were taken by addressing SEAFO on the issue of observer training and observer availability. SEAFO already facilitates training programs to make Contracting Parties able to comply with its requirements of vessels carrying scientific observers onboard. As the operators involved in this MR2 are currently not active in the area, the availability of observers is only relevant in potential future resuming of fishing activity in the area. The programs provided by SEAFO satisfy the need of the operators in case of resuming activities. Therefore, although the action is not achieved, the OT is considered finalized.	1
ER score		1

C.2 Compliance

This item of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. In the described audit framework, this is measured through three components - completeness, timeliness, and source quality.

The summary of these analyses will provide a Compliance Index (CI) that will be reported in the audit summary. This will inform both the Authority and Operators about the level of achievement (including gaps, limitations, etc.).

OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks (obligatory)

For the OT 2.1, the compliance assessment is presented in Table 20, where three components of compliance are analysed and scored.

Table 20 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT2.1.

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	The proposal was presented to the SEAFO SC, but there was no support for developing a pilot project. No data were specified to be collected to assess this OT. With better indicators, data could have been specified and gathered to assess this outcome target.	2
Timeliness Level (T)	The MR2 did not specify timing, but both the dialogue and the pilot project was supposed to take place in the FarFish lifetime. A dialogue has been established, but development of the current e-logbook system was not considered necessary by SEAFO.	4
Source quality Level (S)	The involved parties MFMR and SEAFO are relevant for the purpose of the dialogue for the reporting via e-logbook. The pilot project is not considered relevant at this time due to the fishing activity. Yet, no data or analysis were specified to be collected in the MR.	2
Total CI Score		2,7

OT 2.2 All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals (obligatory)

Regarding the transmission of AIS and VMS signals for all vessels, specified in OT2.2., the compliance assessment is presented in Table 22, for each of the compliance parameters.

Table 21 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT2.2.

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	MR2 reported that there was no VMS data of EU vessels in the SEAFO database and that the AIS data collected from both Global Fishing Watch and SEEAFO was incomplete (not detailed enough). CSIC was therefore not able to include this CS in their analysis.	2
Timeliness Level (T)	The MR2 did not specify timing but this was supposed to be completed in the FarFish lifetime. Actions were taken to carry out the analysis, but due to lack of data it was not possible to perform the action.	2
Source quality Level (S)	Actions were taken by CSIC, as originally planned. Yet, neither AIS nor VMS data were available to perform it.	1
Total CI Score		1,7

OT 2.3 All vessels have onboard observers (recommended)

Finally, for OT2.3 on onboard observer, the compliance assessment focuses solely on the activities done within the FarFish project to accomplish the target. In this regard, the FarFish project found that SEAFO is already providing some of the needed activities to achieve this target: The project reports on this and as no further actions will be required, the actions are consider finalized.

Table 22 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT2.3.

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	A dialogue was established with SEAFO about developing observer training. SEAFO facilitates comprehensive training programs for observers that could be implemented in the event of increasing fishing activity by the EU fleet. With no further action were needed from FarFish, the action is then complete.	5
Timeliness Level (T)	The MR2 did not specify timing of the training program, but it was supposed a be completed in the FarFish lifetime. No training program was developed in the FarFish project. SEAFO facilitated a training program for observers in May 2019. With no further interest from EU operators the action is considered finalized.	5
Source quality Level (S)	SEAFO as the relevant authority for this area provided the training. The FarFish project established the dialogue to ensure that the needs of the operators were met in the event of future resuming of fishing activities.	5
Total CI Score		5

D. MR Effects

This item of the audit aims to evaluate the impact of the MR in monetary terms. Ideally, a cost-benefit analysis of the MR should have been performed. In the SEA case, none of the OTs are relevant for a quantitative cost-benefit analysis. The MRs for the selected case study are not aimed at managing the fisheries, but rather focus on very limited areas within MCS of the fisheries. The impacts of the OTs are therefore difficult to ascertain and isolate from other factors. We have therefore qualitatively discussed expected impacts as introduced in the methodological section. Both the costs and benefits arising from the actions associated with each of the outcome targets are to a little extent studied within the project.

OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks (obligatory)

The actions associated with this OT have to an extent been carried out, but there have been no changes to the current situation. SEAFO already have an electronic system and did not see development and implementation of a new system as necessary. Thus, there are very minor economic impacts from this OT and the associated activities. Likely minor costs have been incurred from discussions with SEAFO.

Creating a pilot project for ERS and training programme would imply costs for the actors involved, however the likelihood of being implemented is highly uncertain and cost allocation between states, vessels and other parties is uncertain.

OT 2.2 All vessels transmit AIS or VMS signals (obligatory)

Activities have been carried out within the FarFish project, but these have not led to changes in the current fishing or management operations. Thus, the economic impacts are negligible. Minor costs have been incurred by FarFish, SEAFO and GFW in acquiring data and analysing these. No benefits have so far been realized.

Receiving vessel position data may bring benefits through Improving MCS of fisheries. These may be utilized through more effective monitoring of vessels and may allow for better economic yield from the fisheries in the long term. As the current fisheries are very limited, and available quotas are underutilized, the potential for improvement is also small. The benefits should be balanced against the cost involved in introducing and enforcing the different measures.

OT 2.3 All vessels have onboard observers (recommended)

Only minor scoping activities have been carried out within the FarFish project and there have been no changes to the fisheries or management activities. Thus, the economic impacts are again negligible.

Onboard observers are relatively expensive, and the net benefit should be assessed, also taking alternative observing systems into account. McElderry et al (2003⁵) investigated onboard and remote sensing systems in the British Columbia halibut longline fishery and estimated observers to cost 450 USD/day for each vessel. Actual costs in the SEA fishery are likely to be less. Who bears the costs of the observers varies. The benefits from observers may arise from better utilization of the fisheries resources. If the private profit from the fishery is marginal and vessels bear a considerable part of the observer costs, this may reduce the incentive to fish and thus value adding.

The benefits from these measures are difficult to ascertain, but there may be positive long-term impacts on the sustainability of the fisheries and improved management may provide considerable economic benefits.

4.3 Summary of the audit

Table 23 presents a summary of the audit of SEA MR version 2. All OTs are finalised, and no further action will take place. At a practical level, the OTs and related indicators are scored with a relatively low level of achievements. This should be considered more as a result of the audit framework than the performance of the action taken place in the CS. As stated in the introduction, and in the MR2, this has to be considered a theoretical exercise, in a case with limited fishery and a well-functioning RFMO. The proposed actions, for a pilot study to introduce e-logbooks and to develop and complete a training program for observers for the coastal member states of SEAFO, were initiated. In the current situation, these programs were not implemented, but their relevance and procedures for how to propose them has been established.

⁵ McElderry, H. J. Schrader, and J. Illingworth. 2003. The Efficacy of Video-Based Electronic Monitoring for the Halibut Longline Fishery. Fisheries and Oceans Canada Research Document 2003/042.

Table 23 Audit dashboard: Summary of evaluation of CS2 Southeast Atlantic MR2

	PHASE		OT 2.1	OT 2.2	OT 2.3
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1			
	Documentation system	Crit. 2			
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant			
Responsive Assessment					
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER			
	Compliance Assessment	CI			
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			On-going	Finalized	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment				
	Final assessment				

5 CS3: SFPA: Cape Verde

5.1 General remarks

The Management Recommendations (MR2) for the SFPA with Cape Verde was submitted on March 15th, 2021. The audit process is thereafter initiated.

Cape Verde and the EU have signed a Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) allowing EU vessels from Spain, Portugal, and France to fish in Cape Verde waters. The first SFPA between the EU and Cape Verde dates to March 2007. The current SFPA was signed on May 20th, 2019. The legal framework behind the agreement is based on *Art. 62 UNCLOS*⁶ where coastal states should assess their fishing capacity and allow other states to catch the surplus in their EEZ through agreements. The protocol covers a period of five years (2019-2024). It provides fishing opportunities for a maximum of 69 EU vessels to fish in Cape Verdean waters, based on the best available scientific advice and following the recommendations of the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT). Cape Verde is also offering fishing opportunities to fishing vessels from other states, and the following nationalities have a license to fish; Japan (8 vessels), Senegal (6 vessels), El Salvador (4 vessels), Curaçao (3 vessels), Panama (2 vessels) and Belize (1 Vessel).

The main objectives of the MR2 for Cape Verde are stated in section 1.5 of the MR2 document and are: to improve data collection and data monitoring for sustainable fisheries, especially for the species of blue shark and swordfish.

5.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendation (MR)

A. MR Implementation

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. This stage is broken down in two phases: a documentation system conformance analysis (A.1) and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

For MR2 for Cape Verde will be audited in terms of the documentation system based on the Deliverable 3.5 “General Guidelines for making MRs” (Viðarsson et al., 2019), D3.5 with the “Second MR Invitation” (Viðarsson et al., 2020), drawing on the results from D5.2 with the recommendations from the audit

⁶ https://www.un.org/Depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf

of MR1 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2019) and input from the "Report on challenges and suggestions for improvements"(Arias-Hansen et al., 2020). The auditors will evaluate the development from the first MR for Cape Verde (Mikkelsen et al., 2020) to the present MR2.

AUTHORITIES

The authorities reported in MR2 are MATIS with the addition of IMAR as the CS leader, taking the role as lead representing authorities. They obtain input from relevant authorities as the National Directorate of Maritime Economy (DNEM) in Cape Verde, the Directorate-General for Marine Resources (DGRM) and Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE) for the EU. These entities were considered sufficient representation in MR1; therefore, the auditor considers that the authority role continuous to be sufficiently represented and the role is clearly defined in MR2.

OPERATOR

MR2 states that the operators qualified to participate are ANFACO-CECOPESCA, ORPAGU and LDAC, as operator representative. WP4 is the representative of the operators within the project, led by UiT and the Cape Verde CS leader IMAR. The partner operators' description has been updated according to what was requested in MR1. ANFACO-CECOPESCA and OPAGAC (represented by LDAC) have been adequately included.

The MR1 audit recommended a list of implicated vessels to be presented. This is not provided for MR2. However, there are clear statements in other sections of the MR2 about active participation and interaction between stakeholders, including additional relevant operators such as ATUNLO and FRESKOMAR, which suggests that actions have been taken to promote involvement from operators

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

The main objective of the MR2 is to improve data collection and monitoring for sustainable fisheries, especially for the species of blue shark and swordfish. This improvement can be broken down into two main areas, first data collection, aiming to improve the collection and analysis of bycatch data on these two species, and second data monitoring, by supporting enforcement by utilising latest available satellite systems. The goal of the MR2 has been made more specific by defining these two areas of action, namely data collection and monitoring. By specifically defining two areas of actions, the aim of the MR more closely relates to the identified challenges defined in Section 5 of the MR2, which enables the auditor to verify compliance.

The MR1 audit emphasised the need to strive for active participation of stakeholders to ensure that the OTs contribute to the challenges of this fisheries. MR2 reports several efforts to strive for continuous contact with relevant operators, in the form of physical and virtual meetings described in Sections 1.3 and 1.4.1. The auditor considers that these efforts satisfy the recommendation made in MR1 audit and further, recommends that they should continue throughout the life of the project. The auditor highlights that these efforts should attempt to establish periodic forums where operators can

actively participate in the management initiatives in Cape Verdean fisheries agreements, even after the FarFish project.

OUTCOME TARGETS (OTs) AND INDICATORS

In the MR2 from Cape Verde, a revision of the OTs and related indicators and strategies was conducted, therefore an update of the audit is required. The auditor will evaluate each OT to verify whether actions have been taken towards resolving the issues found in the MR1 audit.

A summary of the OTs and indicators defined in the MR2 for Cape Verde is presented in Table 24 below, indicating the management objectives they relate to. The OTs were modified and rearranged from MR1. OT 3.4 was renumbered to OT3.2 with minor rewording. OT3.2 and 3.3 were changed to 3.3 and 3.4 respectively, with important rewording to provide a more concrete target for 3.3 and a broader scope of analysis for 3.4.

Table 24 CS3 Cape Verde: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators

Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Improve data collection in conformity with ICCAT on directed catch and bycatch of swordfish and blue shark	OT 3.1. A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data. Obligatory	I_1_CS3 Data flow described - Indicator Cat. C I_2_CS3 Improved data recording in e-logbooks of all catches (target- and bycatches) - Indicator Cat. C I_3_CS3 Harmonised protocol designed - Indicator Cat. C I_4_CS3 Harmonised protocol implemented - Indicator Cat. C
Improve the use of observer data and feed it into stock assessment in the context of ICCAT	OT 3.2: All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals Obligatory	I_5_CS3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geo-localization – Indicator Cat. A I_6_CS3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geo-localization - Indicator Cat. A
Improve knowledge in the value chain, processing, and market conditions	OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place Recommended	I_7_CS3 Observer program established - Indicator Cat. C I_8_CS3 Observer program in place - Indicator Cat. C
Improve knowledge in the value chain, processing, and market conditions	OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided Recommended	I_9_CS3 Information on catches and landings provided - Indicator Cat. C I_10_CS3 Information on processing and trade provided - Indicator Cat. C

OT 3.1. *A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data.*

The OT3.1 text remained unmodified from how it was defined in MR1. The auditor considers this is adequate as the MR1 audit stated the OT was already rephrased to be made more specific. The auditor considers that this OT is key for this CS, as it relates directly to the main goal of the MR2. The MR1 audit recommended the inclusion of more indicators to better follow up the performance of the OT. This recommendation was considered in MR2, the OT has now four indicators that relate to the progress of the OT. Therefore, the auditor considers that these indicators respond to the recommendation made in the MR1 audit.

Also, in the MR1 audit, it was mentioned that one of the operators suggested harmonizing SFPa and ICCAT data only relying on Flag and coastal states to submit data according to the EU and ICCAT in isolation. However, the reports of achievement of this OT have determined that the actions required to advance in the harmonization of catch data protocol were possible even without narrowing down the task, as it was suggested. Therefore, the auditor considers that the comments made in the first audit were considered, but not determinant for advancing on this OT.

Finally, in MR1 the existing management measures within the national management plan, the SFPa and within ICCAT, that relate to the harmonization task, were identified. The auditor recommended mentioning these measures in the analysis of the OT in the MR1 audit. The auditor found that in the reported progress of the OT and in the recommended actions, the management measures and organizations involved were stated. The auditor considers that this satisfies the recommendation.

OT 3.2: *All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals*

This OT was previously numbered as OT3.4 and audited as such in the MR1 audit. The main concern of the auditor was a reported issue regarding Cape Verde's capacity to process the data, as some incompatibilities issues were found in their systems. This issue is reported to be solved in MR2, which satisfies the auditor's concern. Also, for this OT, relevant management measures were identified for the relevant management plans (National, SFPa and ICCAT) in MR1. The auditor suggested to mention them in the analysis of the OT. MR2 does not specifically mention the management measures as recommended. However, it highlights the reasons for this OT to be defined as obligatory, which relates to these measures. The auditor considers that, due to the reported difficulties with obtaining the data from national authorities, a more specific mention of the importance to fulfil the management measures related to this OT could serve to add relevance to the task and obtain the needed data.

OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place

The OT3.3. which was numbered OT3.2 in MR1 is a recommended outcome target, therefore it was not audited in the MR1 audit. The wording of the OT was modified from “Setting of conditions for a better coordination of observer programme: content (protocols, criteria), schedules, processes, sharing of information” to “Strengthened scientific observer program in place”. The auditor considers that in terms of the SMART analysis, the rewording made the OT more specific. As this OT was not audited in MR1 the SMART analysis will be conducted in full.

Table 25 SMART analysis OT3.3.

Specific	It is OK. It clearly states the aim to tackle a specific issue
Measurable	The indicators provide stages of development which add measurability to the OT
Assignable	Responsible entities are made clear in text, yet difficulties were found in the implementation phase due to lack of provision in Cape Verdean legislation.
Relevant	Yes. The challenge has been identified and the OT contributes to improve it.
Time	Yes, within the lifetime of the FarFish project.

OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided

The OT3.4. which was numbered OT3.3 in MR1 is a recommended outcome target, therefore it was not audited in the MR1 audit. The wording of the OT was modified from “Increase knowledge and data collection of trade flows to include for example destination, utilization, quantity, value” to “trade flow data provided”. The auditor considers that in terms of the SMART analysis, the rewording made the OT more specific. As this OT was not audited in MR1, a SMART analysis will be conducted.

Table 26 SMART analysis OT3.4.

Specific	Yes, it clearly states the goal to attain. The objective, key activities and indicators add specificity to the OT.
Measurable	The key activities inform that the data is for all tuna vessels operating in Cape Verde. This should be indicated in text of the OT as it does not refer to other fleets other than tuna. Suggested text “Trade flow data on tuna provided”
Assignable	The indicators mention the responsible entities
Relevant	Yes, the OT tackles the challenge of data availability identify in this CS
Time	Yes, within the life of the FarFish project.

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

The only OT addressing socioeconomic issues is OT 3.4, on the provision of trade flow data. Most of the actions defined for achieving this OT consists of collecting and building the data from primary sources. No baseline data is available and hence, it is not feasible to conduct a sensitivity analysis for audit purposes.

B. Summary Documentation System Conformance Audit

To finalize this stage of the audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 27. The audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 40.

Table 27 CS3 Cape Verde: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

Outcome Target	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated are available to implement a reliable program.	
	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 3.1. A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data. Obligatory	The catch data and protocols evaluated for harmonization fulfil the requirements to accomplish the defined indicators			
OT 3.2: All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals Obligatory	The data required to fulfil the indicators defined for this OT is relevant to accomplishing it. However, difficulties to collect it from the relevant authorities were reported. This increases the risk of not accomplishing the OT			
OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place. Recommended	The data analysed and the produced training materials reported as developed for this OT are relevant to fulfil the indicators.			
OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided. Recommended	The data and methods specified to obtaining it are attainable and relevant to the selected indicators for this OT			

C. MR Audit and adaptation

The RBM proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for such responsiveness and adaptation of the MR. There are two phases to support this stage, effectiveness performance and compliance evaluation.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

OT3.1. *A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data. **Obligatory***

To verify the performance of OT3.1, the operator and authorities have agreed upon four indicators as shown in Table 24. A progress report is presented in section 6.3 of the MR2, with an indication of the level of achievement and the main risks. According to it, the auditors will evaluate the effectiveness performance for each of the selected indicators in Table 28, and assign the ER score according to the audit results.

Table 28 performance indicators for OT3.1 in Cape Verde

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_1_CS3 Data flow described - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 states that an analysis of the relevant data collection systems for EU tuna fisheries in Cape Verde was completed. The data flow analysed and described was then utilised for developing a suggested harmonized data protocol, presented in Appendix 1 of the MR2. The indicator is reported as achieved. The auditor considers that the activities carried out were sufficient to accomplish the OT.	5
I_2_CS3 Improved data recording in e-logbooks of all catches (target- and bycatches) - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 reports that the data recording has been improved and that blue shark is now listed as species in the e-logbook. Also, that the implementation of a compatible system with e-logbook data from EU vessels which had been an ongoing issue since 2015 is reported solved. These reports constitute improvements to data recording, considering the text of the OT and the reported challenges in this CS. The activities performed to achieve indicator 1 also contributed to achieve indicator 2 which indicates effectiveness in performance. The indicator is reported as achieved. The auditor considers that sufficient and relevant actions have been taken.	5
I_3_CS3 Harmonised protocol designed - Indicator Cat. C	The achievement report in MR2 indicates that a suggested harmonized data protocol has been develop and that is presented in Appendix 1. The harmonized protocol is based on the results from the data flow analysis reports in indicator I_1_CS3. Existing resources were utilized to accomplish this indicator as it states the EU e-logbook contained required information on swordfish and blue shark, as well as other relevant data.	5

I_4_CS3 Harmonised protocol implemented - Indicator Cat. C	The indicator is reported as not achieved, and MR2 states that it will not be achieved during the life of the FarFish project. Nevertheless, the auditor found important steps and recommendations in the MR2 document related to the effectiveness of the actions to contribute towards achieving this indicator. First, the progress report suggests specific short- and long-term actions involving relevant entities where Cape Verde as member can commit to implement data harmonisation protocols, such as the JSC and ICCAT. Also, in the report on the achievement indicates that concrete actions are undergoing from the side of ICCAT to harmonization data from tuna fisheries, which related to the specified long-term actions described. The auditor considers that MR2 provides a clear roadmap to accomplish this indicator.	3
Total ER score		4,5

OT 3.2: All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals. Obligatory

The progress report for OT3.2 which refers to AIS and/or VMS signals transmitted by all vessels operating in Cape Verde, is presented in section 6.4 in the MR2. The document indicates that these two indicators cannot be evaluated as the necessary data to conduct the analysis has not been obtained. The report also states that FarFish project has requested the data to the relevant authority. Yet the authorization to release it, due to confidentiality issues, has not been obtained. One of the challenges reported in MR1, referring to technical issue in Cape Verde to receive VMS signals, has been solved and national authorities are receiving data from both EU and Non-EU vessels. Finally, the MR2 states that if data is made available, the results can be provided within the life of the project.

Considering the similarity of the indicators and the activities done to accomplish them, the two indicators will be evaluated together. The score will be assigned individually, if any consideration is found to differentiate the evaluation, this will be stated in text presented in Table 29.

Table 29 performance indicators for OT3.2 in Cape Verde

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_5_CS3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geolocalization – Indicator Cat. A	The auditor considers that although these two indicators are not achieved yet, and considering the major challenge faced with data availability, the actions taken have been positive. The functioning of the Cape Verdean system for VMS transmission is a major outcome. The report on all fleets reporting in time record adds transparency. As the purpose of the OT was to increase pressure to all operators and related entities to add transparency to the fisheries in Cape Verde, the effectiveness of the actions has been considerable. The auditor recommends following up on the data availability to report on the potential achievement of the indicators should be included. Otherwise, a roadmap for the Cape Verdean authorities to carry out the analysis	3
I_6_CS3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant		3

(AIS+VMS) geolocalization - Indicator Cat. A	themselves with a commitment to communicate the results in the joint committee is suggested.	
Total ER score		3

OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place. Recommended

For the OT3.3. on strengthening the scientific observer program, two indicators were defined in MR2. Section 6.5 of the MR2 reports on the progress of the activities carried out to accomplish these indicators. The auditors present the correspondent performance evaluation for each of the indicators in Table 30.

Table 30 performance indicators for OT3.3 in Cape Verde

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_7_CS3 Observer program established - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 reports that this indicator is achieved. Appendix 2 of the MR2 document presents the materials produced for training observers in the necessary activities on-board. In addition, a database was developed with IMAR in Cape Verde to facilitate data storage, processing, and compilation. The auditor finds that the appendix 2 is unclear and requires a sharper picture of the self-sampling scheme to be provided. This said, the auditors find that the actions taken towards achieving this indicator are positive and can contribute to strengthening the observer program, as stated in the OT. The auditor recommends including more detailed information and examples of the materials developed for the self-sampling project and how it fits into the observer program.	4
I_8_CS3 Observer program in place - Indicator Cat. C	The MR2 states that this indicator will not be achieved in the life of the FarFish project, due to the lack of provisions for scientific observers in the Cape Verdean legislation. Yet, several actions have been taken and recommendations provided to support it. The main actions reported towards putting in place an observer program in Cape Verde were found in the reports of achievement (in this recommended OT3.3, but also in the reports and actions for the obligatory OT3.1, as the observer program is key for the long-term implementation of a harmonized protocol on catches data collection). The auditor considers that the actions and recommended steps reported are relevant and effective if implemented. However, the implementation of the program itself requires active collaboration and commitment from the skippers and crew from all the international fleet, but also direct action by the relevant legislative body in Cape Verde.	3
Total ER score		3,5

OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided. Recommended

Finally, the performance evaluation for the OT3.4 is done for the two indicators defined, to providing trade flow data as shown in Table 31. The progress report for this OT is found in section 6.6. of the Cape Verdean MR2.

Table 31 performance indicators for OT3.4 in Cape Verde

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_9_CS3 Information on catch and landings provided - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 reports that several data bases have been consulted, relevant information has been obtained and analysed. Further, reports on interviews conducted with relevant stakeholders have been reported. The level indicator is reported as complete, and it indicated that the data on catches and landings was obtained through the reported means. However, two issues arise. Firstly, MR2 does not state how the data has been processed and how the discrepancies found in the catch data were dealt with. However, the MR2 also states that a pending analysis of the trade flow of tuna should be published on month 52 of the FarFish project. As this analysis will be published, the auditor considers that this contributes to the achievement of the OT in the provision of trade flow data, yet until the document is published, this cannot be assessed. The steps and actions described show effective actions towards collection of the data, the use of this data is yet to be evaluated.	4
I_10_CS3 Information on processing and trade provided - Indicator Cat. C	In line with the analysis of indicator I_9_CS3, MR2 states that an analysis of the trade flow of tuna is pending and should be publish on month 52 of the FarFish project. This analysis aims to provide the processing and trade information. The progress of this analysis is reported to be heavily based on interview as trade flow data is not available. MR2 reports that some interviews have already been conducted and more are to be scheduled. As this analysis will be published, the auditors consider that this contributes to the achievement of the OT in the provision of trade flow data. Yet until the document is published, this cannot be assessed. The steps and actions described show effective actions towards collection of the data, the use of this data is yet to be evaluated.	3
Total ER score		3,5

C.2 Compliance

This item of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. In the described audit framework, this is measured through three components - completeness, timeliness, and source quality. The summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (C.I) that will be reported in the audit summary.

OT 3.1. A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data (obligatory).

According to the progress report of the OT3.1 in MR2, the compliance assessment is presented in Table 32. The three components are evaluated and scored separately.

Table 32 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT3.1. in Cape Verde

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	According to the performance assessment above, all documentation required to design a harmonized catch data protocol has been analysed. All indicators except indicator I_4_CS3, which refers to the implementation of the harmonized protocol, are fully accomplished. A roadmap is provided to aim for the implementation of the OT indicating the relevant organizations to consult and include in this process. The auditor assigned a high level of completeness to the OT.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	The MR2 does not specify a time for accomplishing this OT. Yet, considering the lifetime of the project, the harmonization of catch data reporting has advanced well. According to the progress report in section 6.3, only indicator I_4_CS3 will not be achieved. However, considering that the implementation of the protocol is outside of the authority of the FarFish project, this auditor considers the timeliness of the OT is satisfactory.	4
Source quality Level (S)	The identified data collections systems are described in the progress report as the EU e-logbook system, the logbook defined in the SFPA (paper-based), the Cape Verdean fisheries data collection system, and a proposed e-logbook and observer scheme developed with support from DG MARE. The quality of sources analysed are relevant for the OT. MR2 further recommends that ICCAT implements this harmonised data collection system and promotes electronic reporting, which refer to achieving indicator 3.4. According to the data flow reported in figure 3 of the MR2, ICCAT is the relevant entity to convey the data transmission from the operators. The auditor considers that the sources analysed are relevant and sufficient for a harmonised catch data reporting system.	5
Total CI Score		4,3

OT 3.2: All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals (obligatory)

For the OT3.2 regarding transmission of AIS and/or VMS signals, the main challenge found was the lack of access to data from the national authorities. The auditors therefore evaluate the three components of compliance in terms of the activities developed by the project regardless of the data availability. Table 33 shows the compliance assessment results.

Table 33 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT3.2. in Cape Verde

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	The OT cannot be evaluated because the data has not been shared by the relevant authorities. The auditor highlights that MR2 reports that the incompatibility issues reported in MR1 are now solved and the Cape Verdean authorities are receiving data from the ERS in time record. However, until data is shared, the OT will not be completed, therefore the completeness level is set to a medium level.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	MR2 mentions that the results from this OT should be conveyed in the lifetime of the project. Also, it states that, if the data is made available within the project lifetime, the OT could be accomplished. The auditors highlight the efforts of the project to collect this data and further, recognizes the constrains related to data confidentiality and authorization processes. If the data is not released within the lifetime of the project, the auditor suggests providing a more detailed progress report in the final MR, with mention of the number of communications sent to the relevant authorities, including the date of the exchange. This will allow the update of the task once the project is finished.	3
Source quality Level (S)	The VMS data is received by COSMAR (maritime security operation centre) and managed by IGP (General inspection of fisheries). These are the relevant entities to address for the VMS data in Cape Verde. Yet, until the data is released, the source quality level can only be scored to a medium level.	3
Total CI Score		3

OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place (recommended)

Regarding the strengthening of the scientific observer program as stated in OT3.3, the compliance assessment evaluates the materials developed by the FarFish project and made available for implementation. The results of this assessment are shown in Table 34.

Table 34 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT3.3. in Cape Verde

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	MR2 reports that materials such as manuals, sampling protocols and a self-sampling program, as well as a training guides have been produced by CCMAR in cooperation with Cape Verdean scientists. The auditor considers that these activities contribute towards achieving the OT. Yet, the implementation of the program requires a provision in the national legislation. The importance of implementing the produced material is highlighted in MR2, with mention of the responsibilities that Cape Verde has under ICCAT.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	The training and material have been produced, as reported in MR2. An action plan is described for the implementation and testing of the program and provision for the long-term stability of the program. There is no further mention of frequency or follow up actions. Considering that the provisions for an observer program in the Cape Verdean legislation is outside of the FarFish project scope.	5
Source quality Level (S)	MR2 mentions that the training materials, manuals, and protocols are currently used in the EU national observer program and that a databased was developed in collaboration with IMAR in Cape Verde to facilitate data storage and processing. Considering that the materials are taken from an observer program that is in functional and in place and further collaboration was established with relevant parties in Cape Verde.	5
Total CI Score		4,7

OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided (recommended)

Finally, for the OT3.4 about the provision of trade flow data, the compliance assessment was based on the progress report presented in MR2. According to this section, most of the activities to achieve this OT are currently being conducted and will be delivered within the lifetime of the project. This is portrait in the compliance assessment report presented in Table 35.

Table 35 Assessment of three component of the compliance audit for OT3.4. in Cape Verde

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	OT3.4 is defined as trade flow data. Two layers of information are defined in the selected indicators for this OT. First layer is data on catches and landings and the second is information on processing and trade. MR2 reports that catches, and landings are provided and that information on processing and trade is in progress. MR2 reports on interviews, and more are planned. The auditors recognize the constrains to conducting interviews during COVID-19 pandemic.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	MR2 reports that the latter is likely to be finished by June and the final report by September 2021, in line with the FarFish project timeline. This report will be available in time to provide the trade data flow. The auditors recommend that the results of the reports are summarized in	4

	the final MR for Cape Verde, with mention on how this data will be further utilized.	
Source quality Level (S)	MR2 reports that landing site information was obtained from UNIDO. Further information was obtained from three major processing firms utilizing tuna from foreign fleets. The raw material sourcing, processing type, and general product mix of these firms are provided in the ex-post, ex-ante evaluation report from the Joint Scientific Committee. Furthermore, export statistics from the ITC (International Trade Centre) were used to identify product types and destination countries for tuna products from Cape Verde. For the processing and trade data, interviews are being conducted with fleet representatives and processing informants. The auditor considers the sources are relevant for the goal of the OT.	4
Total CI Score		4

D. MR Effects

The effects of the MR will be assessed by conducting a qualitative assessment of the potential costs and benefits that the implementation of the OTs and associated activities for the partners involved in the analysed fisheries.

OT 3.1. *A harmonized catch data protocol in place that facilitates improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data (obligatory).*

The harmonisation of catch data protocol was considered as a main priority both for the authorities and the operators. This is reflected in the reports of actions towards this task in MR2 and the quality of the documentation provided. The costs of developing the harmonised protocol have been incurred, leaving the costs of implementation pending. The benefits from implementing this action, can yield important benefits for both operators and authorities. The qualitative analysis of the potential costs and benefits from implementing the OT3.1 are reported in Table 36.

Table 36 Analysis of potential costs and benefits from OT3.1.

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Harmonisation protocol developed	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Implementation of harmonised protocols	Cost	Small to medium - Related to efficiency	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long

Reduced capacity employed	Benefit	Uncertain	Vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Improved control and inspection procedures	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Improved stock assessments	Benefit	Highly uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Long
Improved stock status	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Medium and long
Improved yield from fisheries	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners and trickle effects to society	Long

OT 3.2: All vessels transmit AIS and/or VMS signals (obligatory)

The data has not been yet made available for achieving OT3.2. If the data is received, and the data analysis can be carried out, the costs would be modest, as they will be bear by the FarFish project. In comparison, the result from this analysis could benefits by contributing to add a powerful tool to the monitoring of the fishery. Furthermore, the benefits of knowledge improvement and the potential to utilise this tool in future management and control can also be counted.

Table 37 Analysis of potential costs and benefits from OT3.2.

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Data collection and analysis	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Implementation of data analysis process	Cost	Small to medium - Related to efficiency	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Reduced capacity employed	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities	Short-medium and long
Coupling data analysis with monitoring and enforcement	benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Enhanced legal rent in fisheries by fighting IUU	Benefit	Highly uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Long
Improved stock status	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Medium and long
Improved yield from fisheries	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners and trickle effects to society	Long

OT 3.3: Strengthened scientific observer program in place (recommended)

Strengthening of the observer program through developing training material, self-sampling protocols and guidelines is an activity of relative low cost that has already been incurred by the project FarFish. The efficiency of the use of resources was considered by utilizing resources already utilized by the EU national observer program and adapting to the need of Cape Verde through cooperation with local organizations. The implementation of the program could represent a medium to higher cost, considering the efficiency of the management actions. The most considerable cost would be to include a provision for the observer program in the national legislation, as the legislative process could be inefficient and time consuming, which can cause delays in the implementation and reduce the potential benefits that a faster action could entail.

Table 38 Analysis of potential costs and benefits from OT3.3.

Impact	Cost/ benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Training materials developed	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Implementing observer program	Cost	Medium	Vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Improved stock assessments	Benefit	Highly uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Long
Improved stock status	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, Vessel owners, society	Medium and long
Improved yield from fisheries	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners and trickle effects to society	Long

OT 3.4: Trade flow data provided (recommended)

OT 3.4 refers to improving the availability of data on trade flow to improve knowledge in the value chain, processing, and market conditions. The costs of the activities required to achieve this OT are low, considering they are borne by the FarFish project. The potential benefits are highly uncertain but relate to taking better advantage of market opportunities and potentially better economic collaboration and partnerships, through added transparency to the market conditions in Cape Verde. Promoting cooperation among economic operators can yield medium- to long-term benefits to the fisheries, with potential trickle-down effect to the broader society.

Table 39 Analysis of potential costs and benefits from OT3.4.

Impact	Cost/ benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Collection and analysis of trade flow data	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Implement an annual trade data report	Cost	Medium to high – related to efficiency	National authorities, economic operators	Short-medium and long
Improved collaboration among economic operators	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners, economic operators, trickle down to society	Short-medium and long

5.3 Summary of the Audit

Table 40 presents a summary of the audit of the CS3, on the Cape Verdean SFPA MR version 2. For OT 3.1 with the harmonised protocol for bycatch reporting, the work is well advanced, yet implementation by the national authorities is missing. Lack of data to conduct the compliance analysis for OT 3.2 is hindering the development of the action. Other actions such as those for OT3.3 for strengthening the observer’s program are also completed to a large extent, yet implementation is hindered by the lack of a provision for the observer program in the national legislation. This is unlikely to be completed within the lifetime of the project. OT 3.4. with the provision of trade flow data is well advanced and final reporting is pending, although it is planned within the lifetime of the project.

Table 40 Audit dashboard: Summary of the evaluation of CS3 Cape Verde MR2

PHASE			OT 3.1	OT 3.2	OT 3.3	OT 3.4
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1				
	Documentation system	Crit. 2				
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant				
Responsive Assessment						
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER				
	Compliance Assessment	CI				
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			Finalized	On-going	On-going	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment					
	Final assessment					

6 CS4: SFPA: Senegal

6.1 General remarks

The Management Recommendations (MR2) for the SFPA with Senegal was submitted on March 15th, 2021. The audit process is thereafter initiated.

This MR2 for Senegal focuses on the EU Fishery for deep-sea demersal fishery targeting mainly black hake in the Senegalese EEZ. The black hake fishery targets two different species, Tropical African hake (*Merluccius polli*) and Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*). The MR aims to tackle the lack of knowledge about the proportion of the two species caught in Senegalese waters and the bycatch species in this fishery. Also, MR 2 aims to address the need to improve MCS in the area by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools, by utilize onboard observers more efficiently.

6.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendation

A. Analysis of the MR Implementation

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. To conduct this task successfully, an audit of the MR is carried out. This stage is broken down in two phases: a documentation system conformance analysis (A.1) and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

For MR2, the documentation system conformance is audited based on the results from the first audit of MR1 in Deliverable 5.1 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2019) and relevant documentation such as, the “General Guidelines for making MRs” in deliverable 3.5 (Viðarsson et al., 2019), the second MR invitation in Deliverable 3.6 (Viðarsson et al., 2020), the report on challenges and suggestions for improvements in each CS in Deliverable 5.2 (Arias-Hansen et al., 2020). An assessment has been conducted of whether the documentation has been implemented and whether there are any changes (positive or negative), based on evidence from MR2.

AUTHORITIES

The authority is the entity entrusted with the final responsibility for resource management and specifies the outcome targets (OTs) to be reached. MR2 states that MATIS will continue to act as the leading authority within the project while considering input from relevant authorities. In the MR1 the consulting authorities included the Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy (MPEM), Directorate-

General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). In MR2 additional relevant entities have been included namely, Oceanographic Research Centre of Dakar (ISRA-CRODT), and Conservation and Research of West African Aquatic Mammals (COREWAM). In MR1, a risk was stated that the authorities should not represent the reality of the acted authority. Thus, by adding new entities, the authorities have somewhat addressed this risk. In addition, it was stated in the MR1 Audit for Senegal that the communication between MATIS, MPAM and DG MARE took place. Consequently, a workshop reuniting all the relevant entities plus SOPERKA (operator) was organized in October 2019 for developing the MR2. In this way, attention has been drawn for effective communication between the entities.

OPERATOR

SOPERKA is a new operator, which strengthens the representation, as they represent a Senegalese-Spanish company (where LDAC and OPROMAR are associations). In MR1, it was stated that “it is not clear which vessels will be finally involved” but this is solved in MR2: only EU vessels are subject to the MR2. However, there is no list in the MR2 to find out about these vessels, contrary to what was requested in the MR1 audit. By including SOPERKA in the MR2, the auditors assume that this company owns the relevant EU hake trawlers.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

The main goal of the MR2 is to address the lack of knowledge about the proportion of the two hake species caught in Senegalese waters and the bycatch species in this fishery. To achieve this, three objectives were listed: to develop a process that will enable species discrimination and identification for stock assessment, to improve MCS through the use latest satellite tools, and to better utilize onboard observers. These objectives match the challenges stated in MR2 and the audits remarks in MR1, in terms of prioritization of which fishery to address. However, the issues related to hake bycatches from other EU fleets such as shrimp trawlers which emerged from MR1 Audit, have not been clearly stated in the main goals of MR2. Hence, the main goals of the MR2 have partly been made more specific focusing on the black hake fisheries, but some issues such as the fleets targeted to attain the goals remain unclear.

OUTCOME TARGETS AND INDICATORS

Indicators and strategies have been revised in the MR2, compared to MR1 Audit. The auditors analyse the relevance of the changes in this section.

A summary of the Management Objectives, OTs and indicators defined for the Senegalese case is presented in Table 41 below. The Management objectives changed drastically: “*Improved quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement*” and “*Improved input data for sustainable and potentially separate stock assessment of the two species of black hake *M.palli* and *M.senegalensis**” became “*Enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches*”, with more ambitious OTs. This way, proportion of the two hake species are mandatorily provided, as well as bycatch details. The former third management objective (“*Support enforcement by utilizing the*

latest available satellite systems and tools”) has gained in precision: “Support the fight against IUU fishing by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and different kinds of electronic devices, like AIS and VMS”. Finally, OT 4.4 related to improve knowledge in the value chain of the black hake has been added.

Table 41 CS4 Senegal: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators

Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches	<p>OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided.</p> <p>Obligatory</p>	<p>I_1_CS4 Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_2_CS4 Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_3_CS4 Molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. A</p> <p>I_4_CS4 Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires - Indicator Cat. A</p> <p>I_5_CS4 Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling - Indicator Cat. A</p>
	<p>OT 4.2 Bycatch data in black hake fishery available.</p> <p>Obligatory</p>	<p>I_6_CS4 Bycatch data specified by operators in the fishing logbook to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_7_CS4 Observers report, including bycatch data made available to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT and captain of the vessel - Indicator Cat. C</p>
Support the fight against IUU fishing by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and different kinds of electronic devices, like AIS and VMS	<p>OT 4.3 VMS and/or AIS signals are transmitted.</p> <p>Obligatory</p>	<p>I_8_CS4 The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geo-localization – Indicator Cat. B</p> <p>I_9_CS4 The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geo-localization - Indicator Cat. B</p> <p>I_10_CS4 AIS signals have been cross-checked with VMS signals using ISRA-CRODT info as a proxy - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_11_CS4 The comparison between AIS and VMS signals is an accurate and useful method to identify if vessels are compliant - Indicator Cat. C</p>
Improve knowledge in the value chain, processing, and market conditions	<p>OT 4.4 Trade flow data on black hake provided.</p> <p>Recommended</p>	<p>I_12_CS4 Trade flow of hake from EU and Senegalese fleet provided - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Economic data in steps of EU value chain provided - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Information on the potential of hake in the West-African market provided - Indicator Cat. C</p>

OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided (obligatory)

OT 4.1 was previously OT 4.2. By placing it as the first OT illustrates its reassessment in MR2 compared to MR1. In this way, the indicators have been refined. **I_1_CS4** (*Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake*) and **I_2_CS4** (*Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis*) (formerly **I_3_CS4** and **I_4_CS4** in MR1), did not change and are thus, still compatible with the SMART framework. However, the mean of measuring progress has been revised by shifting moving from “A category” indicators (what proportion?) to “C category” indicators (Yes/No). This kind of measurement only partially covers the number of observers and the number of biological samples involved, while proportions would have been more accurate.

I_3_CS4 (*Molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake*) - formerly **I_5_CS4** - has not changed. While the statement is not clear on the actors involved in this task or the related timeline, the obvious connection with the two previous indicators makes it easier to read.

The **I_4_CS4** (*Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires*) and the **I_5_CS4** (*Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling*) are new and therefore, a SMART analysis is required (see Table 15):

Table 42 SMART analysis for I_4_CS4 and I_5_CS4

Specific	Not clear. In text I_4_CS4 does not specify what feedback is required. The auditors assume the purpose is to highlight issues related to implementing the self-sampling protocol by operators and crew. More clarity could be given in text. I_5_CS4 is more specific, and the purpose of the feedback is clearly stated
Measurable	I_4_CS4 . Yes, the category A entails that the indicators should provide the percentage of vessels doing identification that gives feedback in return. I_5_CS4 . Partially, what percentage is to be communicated? The percentage of crew and operators having returns from the molecular analysis or the percentage of satisfactory results from samples?
Assignable	Partly, yet, the entities in charge of the tasks are not stated
Relevant	Yes, the indicators satisfy the need to communicate results to participants in the program
Time	Partly, should follow the identification process

OT 4.2 Bycatch data in black hake fishery available (obligatory)

OT 4.2 was rephrased from “make bycatch data available” to “bycatch data in black hake fishery available”. This is an important change since MR1 audit. First, The OT is moved from OT4.1 to OT4.2, which can portrait a lesser priority given from the parts in obtaining bycatch data compared to obtaining information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches, the current OT4.1.

Second, the rewording of the OT makes it more specific, as it is now completely focused on bycatches in black hake fisheries. Yet, it potentially decreases the relevance of the OT, as data on black hake bycatch from other fleets (such as shrimp trawlers) is now excluded. However, the auditors question the reasons to narrow down the scope of the OT and suggest providing the reasons for it, to avoid lessening the importance of obtaining data on bycatch for this species. The indicators (**I_6_CS4**: *Bycatch data specified by operators in the fishing logbook to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT* and **I_7_CS4**: *Observer’s report, including bycatch data made available to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT and captain of the vessel*) defined for this OT have not changed and therefore, the SMART analysis performed during the first audit remains. The category C to measure achievement for both indicators is sufficient, as the objective of the OT is to make data available and not to obtain the data, which could be measurable in category A (quantitative category).

OT 4.3 VMS and/or AIS signals are transmitted (obligatory)

The two initial indicators defined for this OT remained unchanged (**I_8_CS4**: *The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geo-localization* and **I_9_CS4**: *The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS + VMS) geolocalization*). However, following a remark in the MR1 Audit, the two indicators are now measurable using B category (leveled qualitative categories), while **I_9_CS4** was previously measured with A category (proportion / percentage). The auditors’ comments from the first audit remain, considering that these indicators aim at measuring a proportion, the A category continues to be more appropriate.

In addition, two new indicators have been added. Indicator **I_10_CS4**: *AIS signals have been cross-checked with VMS signals using ISRA-CRODT info as a proxy* and indicator **I_11_CS4**: *The comparison between AIS and VMS signals is an accurate and useful method to identify if vessels are compliant*. These indicators will then be analysed using the SMART method in Table 43.

Table 43 SMART analysis for I_10_CS and I_11_CS

Specific	I_10_CS4 . Yes, the indicator clearly states the action and result I_11_CS4 . No, the text is broad and includes a qualitative evaluation of the data comparison process.
Measurable	I_10_CS4 . Yes, the indicator states that a proxy can be provided. I_11_CS4 . No, the indicator includes a qualitative evaluation of results which is not measurable
Assignable	I_10_CS4 . Yes, MR2 states the entities responsible for cross-checking the data. I_11_CS4 . Partly, it mentioned who is responsible for it but is not clear for whom should the comparison be useful

Relevant	<p>I_10_CS4. Partly, the indicator provides additional knowledge to the OT. However, it is not clear which entities will use this proxy, since the compliance authority is not included</p> <p>I_11_CS4. No, not clear as it entails an evaluation whether this can be considered an indicator at all</p>
Time	<p>I_10_CS4. Yes, within the lifetime of the FarFish project</p> <p>I_11_CS4. Partly, it is assumed that could be evaluated once comparison is made.</p>

Indicator **I_11_CS4** does not satisfy the SMART analysis. The auditor's question whether this indicator could be merged with **I_10_CS4** into a single indicator, considering that **I_11_CS4** is the desired result from **I_10_CS4**. However, the auditor considers that, in **I_10_CS4**, more relevance can be added by clarifying how this proxy will be disseminated, adopted and by which entity, with focus to involving the compliance authority in Senegal.

OT 4.4 Trade flow data on black hake provided (recommended)

This OT was proposed in MR1 but developed in MR2. Therefore, this OT was not audited in MR1. The OT objective is to continue monitoring the black hake beyond the landing stage. Three indicators have been defined to measure achievement of this OT. Indicator **I_12_CS4: Trade flow of hake from EU and Senegalese fleet provided.** Indicator **I_13_CS4: Economic data in steps of EU value chain provided** and **I_14_CS4: Information on the potential of hake in the West-African market provided.** The SMART analysis should be performed for them in Table 44:

Table 44 SMART analysis for I_12_CS, I_13_CS and I_14_CS

Specific	<p>I_12_CS4 Partly, the indicator refers to trade flow data for black hake with focus on the EU and Senegalese fleet. It could be made more specific by defining which data should be provided (e.g. Catches, landings, processing, etc.)</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Partly, economic data in value chain steps is too broad and can be narrow down</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Partly, the relative information linked to the West African market is not mentioned</p>
Measurable	<p>I_12_CS4 Partly, which quantitative indicators are used to determine the trade flow channels? A more specific description will contribute to measurability</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Partly, which economic data is referred to in this indicator? A more specific description will contribute to measurability</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Yes, the relative information linked to the West African market</p>
Assignable	<p>I_12_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2. However, the responsible entity should be revised as it should be ISRA-CRODT</p>

Relevant	<p>I_12_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Yes, the responsible entities are mentioned in MR2. However, the responsible entity should be revised as it should be ISRA-CRODT</p>
Timely	<p>I_12_CS4 Yes, the timeline for the task is provided</p> <p>I_13_CS4 Yes, the timeline for the task is provided</p> <p>I_14_CS4 Yes, the timeline for the task is provided</p>

About category C (Yes / No) measurements, the indicator would seem to indicate that case studies should be carried out. The SMART analysis showed some issues with the definition of the indicators linked to specificity and measurability. For these reasons, the auditors recommend that the indicators for this OT should be rephrased more precisely.

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since the only OT addressing economic issues is OT 4.4 on the provision of trade flow data, most of the actions defined for achieving this OT consists of collecting and building the data from primary sources. No baseline data is available and hence, it is not feasible to conduct a sensitivity analysis for audit purposes.

B.1 Summary Documentation System Conformance Audit

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 45. The audit dashboard with the final audit results of the MR implementation is provided in Table 56 Audit dashboard – Summary of the evaluation of CS4 MR2 Senegal.

Table 45 CS4 Senegal: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

Outcome Target	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.	
	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided (obligatory)	The self-sampling kits, protocols, and training material in relevant languages match with the defined indicators. More clarity can be provided about the data needed to satisfy the two feedback indicators.			
OT 4.2 Bycatch data in black hake fishery available (obligatory)	The logbook template and observer report template satisfy the need to obtain information on by-catch from black hake fisheries. Questions from narrowing down the scope of the OT should be addressed			
OT 4.3 VMS and/or AIS signals are transmitted (obligatory)	The AIS and VMS data correspond to the description of the action. However, the data was not directly provided by the compliance authority which poses a question of how complete the data was. Cross-checking data from authority should be considered.			
OT 4.4 Trade flow data on black hake provided (recommended)	MR2 reports that relevant sources for the needed data. The auditors highlight the need to define the data need more precisely for each of the indicators			

C. MR audit and adaptation

The RBM proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for responsiveness and adaptation of the MR. There are two phases to support this stage, effectiveness performance and compliance evaluation.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

The Auditor should receive evidence about achievement (or not) of the OTs and demonstrate the success or failure to perform the management goals. This analysis will be conducted for each of the defined OTs, with focus on analysing the achievement of each of the indicators:

OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided (obligatory)

To verify the performance of OT4.1, the operator has agreed upon four indicators as shown in Table 4. A progress report is presented in section 5.3 of the MR2. The auditors' evaluation of the effectiveness performance will be carried out for each of the indicators defined for this OT. The Effectiveness Ratio (ER) score is calculated at the end of Table 46, following the general scoring methodology described in section 2.2.

Table 46 OT4.1 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>ER Score</i>
I_1_CS4 Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. C	Observers have been trained to identify the two species. However, there are still identification errors. Artisanal fishermen systematically report all catches as <i>M. senegalensis</i> . The training must be continued.	4
I_2_CS4 Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C	The samples were collected from Spanish and Senegalese fleets (including Senegalese artisanal fleet), referenced, and sent to a laboratory for analysis	5
I_3_CS4 Molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black - Indicator Cat. A	Molecular analysis was carried out in University of Oviedo in 2020, and results were included in MR2 (D4.4)	5
I_4_CS4 Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires - Indicator Cat. A	Both feedbacks (from operators/crew to authorities and inversely) are yet to be happen (scheduled in September 2021)	3

I_5_CS4 Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling - Indicator Cat. A	Both feedbacks (from operators/crew to authorities and inversely) are yet to be happen (scheduled in September 2021)	3
ER Score		4

OT 4.2 *Bycatch data in black hake fishery available (obligatory)*

For OT4.2 on bycatch data in black hake fisheries available, two indicators were defined. The evaluation of the performance effectiveness will be conducted for each of them in Table 47. An Effectiveness Ratio (ER) score will be provided at the end of the table.

Table 47 OT4.2 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_6_CS4 Bycatch data specified by operators in the fishing logbook to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT – Indicator Cat. C	Fishing logbooks from EU vessels are transmitted to IEO, but not yet to ISRA-CRODT due to technical issues. Moreover, the logbook template in the SFPA for the trawl fisheries should be improved. FarFish is proposing a new upgraded version that is likely to be implemented soon.	3
I_7_CS4 Observers report, including bycatch data made available to IEO and/or ISRA-CRODT and captain of the vessel – Indicator Cat. C	Training of observers are likely to happen in 2021 in ISRA-CRODT, to help Senegalese observers' report to reach scientific compliance. Captain's signatures and diffusion from Senegalese authorities to IEO could be implemented immediately.	3
ER Score		3

OT 4.3 *VMS and/or AIS signals are transmitted (obligatory)*

OT4.3 refers to the transmission of VMS and/or AIS signals. For evaluating the performance of this OT; four indicators were defined. The evaluation of the performance effectiveness will be conducted for each of them in Table 48. The ER score will be provided at the end of the table.

Table 48 OT4.3 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_8_CS4 The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geo-localization – Indicator Cat. B	VMS data was not transmitted by the Senegalese compliance authority. However, ISRA-CRODT (which is not the administration in charge of VMS data) was able to provide a list of vessels from which they have received transmissions of VMS signals. Comprehensive AIS data were collected from Global Fishing Watch	3
I_9_CS4 The proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geo-localization – Indicator Cat. B	Since there were no available VMS data provided, the proportion of vessels was not estimated. The MR mentions that if VMS data is made available the action can still be achieved. The auditors suggest striving to involve the compliance authority to obtain VMS before the project's end	2
I_10_CS4 AIS signals have been cross-checked with VMS signals using ISRA-CRODT info as a proxy – Indicator Cat. C	AIS signals have been cross-checked with ISRA-CRODT's list of vessels emitting VMS signals.	4
I_11_CS4 The comparison between AIS and VMS signals is an accurate and useful method to identify if vessels are compliant – Indicator Cat. C	The comparison between AIS and VMS signals, despite uncomplete VMS data, showed its usefulness as a method to identify vessels' compliance	4
ER Score		3,2

OT 4.4 Trade flow data on black hake provided (recommended)

This OT4.4 aims for the provision of trade flow data on the black hake fisheries in Senegal, for evaluating this OT; three indicators were defined. The effectiveness performance evaluation will be conducted for each of them in Table 49. The ER score will be provided at the end of the table.

Table 49 OT4.3 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_12_CS4 Trade flow of hake from EU and Senegalese fleet provided - Indicator Cat. C	Trade flows (volumes and destination) are known for EU vessels (Deliverable 3.4): hakes enter the regular Spanish hake channel. Hake trade flows from Senegalese Fisheries remain little known.	3
I_13_CS4 Economic data in steps of EU value chain provided - Indicator Cat. C	Since hake caught within Senegalese SFPA is included within the vast Spanish hake channel, economic data on the Spanish hake sector is more relevant. Such studies already exist, with no links to FarFish (Antelo, Rodríguez and Villasante, 2012; Secretaría General de Pesca, 2017). MR2 reports progress in this investigation with expected results before the end of the project.	3
I_14_CS4 Information on the potential of hake in the West-African market provided - Indicator Cat. C	Such a study is underway under the responsibility of ISRA-CRODT (end of September 2021). The Auditor reminds the need to verify the responsible entity for this report as in MR UoP is stated as leading the action.	3
ER Score		3

C.2 Compliance

This item of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. A compliance assessment determines whether the specified criterion for the defined indicators is met. This assessment includes a qualitative and quantitative analysis of completeness, timeliness, and quality of the sources of each indicator. The summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (CI) that will be reported in the audit summary. This will inform both the Authority and Operators about the level of achievement (including gaps, limitations, etc.).

OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided (obligatory)

For the OT4.1, MR2 reports on the activities carried out to accomplish this target. The document reports on the development of self-sampling material, including sampling kits, guidelines, and protocols. It further reports that these were implemented in the industrial fleet from the EU as well as in artisanal fisheries. The results from these activities are reported in MR2 in section 5.3. Based on this report, the compliance assessment will be presented in Table 50.

Table 50 OT 4.1 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	The data for the OT was delivered and analysed, so documentation is complete. The results from the surveys to the operators are yet to be submitted.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	The analysis was conducted in due time because results were delivered in time for this audit	5
Source quality Level (S)	The samples were successfully taken by industrial and artisanal fleets. Both these fleets are relevant for implementation of the self-sampling program.	5
Total CI Score		4,6

The OT4.2 refers to the availability of bycatch data in black hake fishery. The activities reported have been done in coordination with the actions taken towards achieving OT4.1, which entails an adequate use of the resources developed within the project. However, some challenges are still found in terms of implementation of a better design logbook template, due to inadequate reporting and lack of trained scientific observers to enhance the quality of the data collected. The MR2 suggest further actions to overcome these challenges. Table 51 presents the compliance evaluation for OT4.2.

Table 51 OT 4.2 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Logbooks' By-catch data are available at IEO, but not yet in ISRA-CRODT. Onboard observers' data are still challenging.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	Training for observers is pending. Issues related to data transmission to ISRA-CRODT are still to be resolved. Logbook data are available at IEO. The action is not likely to be finished within the lifetime of the project, however MR2 indicates that there is a roadmap for implementation beyond the project's end.	3
Source quality Level (S)	There's no cross checking yet between logbook data and observers report. However, an improved logbook template has been presented and relevant authorities are involved for the implementation.	3
Total CI Score		3,3

OT4.3 refers to the transmission of AIS and/o VMS signals. The MR2 reports that AIS data was available, whilst VMS data was only accessible through reports from ISRA-CRODT on a list of vessels transmitting VMS signals with the EEZ coordinates. The compliance evaluation in Table 52 is done considering the progress report and challenges reported in MR2.

Table 52 OT 4.3 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	AIS are fully available. VMS data are not available except a list of vessels who emit in Senegalese waters provided by ISRA-CRODT.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	AIS data and VMS list of vessels were available on time	4
Source quality Level (S)	AIS data come from GFW, which is a proven database. ISRA-CRODT provided coordinates of the EEZ and a list of vessels names that have send transmission. Although ISRA-CRODT is a good source for providing this data, it is not the actual VMS data from the compliance authority. Also, this data would need to be upgraded over time and the VMS' list to be verified with the official VMS data.	3
Total CI Score		3,3

For the provision of trade flow data aimed for in OT4.4, MR2 provides a progress report in section 5.6. According to this, the information required for achieving this OT is being collected and work is being done towards this end. The trade flow data is not yet available but MR2 reports that will be delivered within the lifetime of the project. Table 53 presents the compliance evaluation for this OT.

Table 53 OT 4.4 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Spanish sector is well known, as well as the contribution of black hake. West African sector is still uncovered. Investigations are in progress	3
Timeliness Level (T)	Since this OT was postponed from MR1 to MR2. Investigations are in progress, but results are not available yet. FarFish deliverable D.3.4 already addressed some issues, which will be updated in D3.9 before the end of the project, as MR2 reports.	4
Source quality Level (S)	Black hake catches from EU vessels are well reported by Joint Scientific Committee and Spanish authorities at landing sites. Governmental studies on the Spanish sector have been carried. However, it is hard to trace specific hake from Senegal Black hake catches from Senegalese vessels are reported by national authorities. However, no information emerges on the local sector. In addition, it is ISRA-CRODT that oversees I_14_CS4 and not UoP/NOFIMA, contrary to what was stated in MR2.	3
Total CI Score		3,3

D. MR Effects

This stage of the audit aims to evaluate the impact of the MR in monetary terms. As the available framework documents available to us are not clear, the auditors have interpreted this to the best of our abilities. Ideally, a cost-benefit analysis of the MR should have been performed. Data are often limited and uncertain, as well as the impacts of management measures being difficult to ascertain and isolate from other factors. The MRs for the selected case studies are also not aimed at managing the fisheries, but rather focus on very limited areas within the fisheries and its management. Both the costs and benefits arising from the actions associated with each of the outcome targets are only little related to the project. In the case of Senegal there is an OT relevant for a quantitative cost-benefit analysis (OT4.4), however it arrives at the end of the project, and the temporal inertia inherent in the benefits will not allow the project - relatively short over time - to quantify them. Thus, the auditors have resorted to a qualitative assessment of the OTs and associated activities.

OT 4.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided (obligatory)

The implementing of a protocol to identify the proportion of the two species of black hake in the catches can imply the deployment of a complicated logistic, in terms of distributing training materials, collecting samples, and sending samples to analysis, which could lead to substantial costs. However, the self-sampling protocols have been successfully implemented for two fleets operating in Senegalese waters. The method has proven to be cost-efficient, as the collection of data is satisfactory. Hence, conducting self-sampling protocols, that include training, data collection, analysis and feedbacks are beneficial for all stakeholders, as it leads to improved knowledge of stocks and better management. Proven methodology could be replicable, while the whole process also leads to capacity building for crews and operators.

Table 54 OT4.1 MR effect – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Direct costs associated: samplings	Cost	Small	FarFish and shipowners	Incurred
Direct costs associated: samples analysis	Cost	Small	FarFish and University of Oviedo	Incurred
Improved stocks knowledge	Benefit	Likely high, depending on implementation	RFMOs, National administrations, Operators	Short, medium, and long

Better resource management	Both benefit and cost if a decrease in catch could guarantee stocks sustainability	Likely high, depending on implementation	Operators	Short, medium, and long
Better resource management	Benefit	Likely high, depending on implementation	RFMOs, National administrations	Short, medium, and long
Capacity Building: trained fishermen	Benefit	Small	Fishermen, operators	Short and medium

OT 4.2 Bycatch data in black hake fishery available (*obligatory*)

Bycatch may seriously hamper the stock management of hake. The way this OT is currently set, it only addresses bycatch caught accidentally - and not - during hake fisheries. However, the provision of information about hake as a bycatch from other fisheries (such as shrimp fishing) is essential to guarantee the success of sustainable management of the stocks. It is even a prerequisite for the exploitation of the resource.

In the case of current bycatch in hake fisheries as it is stated in OT 4.2, they are subject to changing regulations to which operators should adapt or even anticipate. The transfer of information, the establishment of a robust and replicable protocol for collecting observer data, as well as the training of observers is a positive step forward in the efficiency of the fishing process.

Table 55 OT4.2 MR effect – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Direct costs associated to data transmission	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Training observers	Cost	Medium	FarFish and participants, National administrations	Short
Boarding observers	Cost	Medium	RFMOs, National administrations and operators	Medium and long
Bycatch are regulated	Cost	Small to medium, depending on the implementation	Operators	Short, medium, and long
Bycatch are regulated	Benefit	Small to medium, depending on the implementation	RFMOs, National Administrations, local fisheries	Short, medium, and long

Better resource management	Benefit	Likely high, depending on the implementation	RFMOs, National administrations, operators, local fisheries	Medium to long
Improved capacity of observers' program	Benefit	Likely medium	RFMOs, National administrations and operators	Medium and long

OT 4.3 VMS and/or AIS signals are transmitted (obligatory)

Since the costs associated to this OT are likely to be low and considering that better access to data is a prerequisite rather than a desirable one-off development, the analysis of the costs and benefits of such actions does not seem relevant.

OT 4.4 Trade flow data on black hake provided (recommended)

The information collected in this OT will be used to carry out a cost-benefit analysis on investments in the domestic hake industry in Senegal and West Africa. The more precise the information in this OT, the more precise this analysis will be, while the costs would be relatively low. The investment potential is certain, given that this fishing industry could have a significant turnover and a positive benefit in terms of development and food security in West Africa.

6.3 Summary of the Audit

The audit dashboard of the second version of the CS4 on the Senegalese SFPA is presented in Table 56. The OT 4.1 about information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches reports extensive and effective work towards achieving the target. The OT has been successfully implemented, achieving broader participation than just the EU fleet. Few actions are pending, one of which is the feedback on the results of the self-sampling program. The OT 4.2 in terms of by-catch data reporting, presents important advancements that are likely to be implemented by the relevant authorities even after the project's end. Some critical actions are still to be taken, the MR2 proposes a roadmap for achieving the target. For the OT 4.3, critical issues with data availability were found, although they were tackled through the provision of documentation by the research institute ISRA-CRODT, which allowed for the analysis to move forward. Some actions are still pending to achieve the OT. Finally, work towards achieving the OT4.4. on trade flow data is well advanced and the final report is expected within the lifetime of the FarFish project.

Table 56 Audit dashboard – Summary of the evaluation of CS4 MR2 Senegal

PHASE			OT 4.1	OT 4.2	OT 4.3	OT 4.4
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1				
	Documentation system	Crit. 2				
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant				
Responsive Assessment			OT 1	OT 2	OT 3	OT 4
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER				
	Compliance Assessment	CI				
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment					
	Final assessment					

7 CS5: SFPA Mauritania

7.1 General remarks

The Management Recommendations (MR2) for the SFPA with Mauritania was submitted to the auditor on April 23rd, 2021. The audit process is thereafter initiated.

MR2 is developed following the “General Guidelines for making MRs” (FarFish, D3.5) and is based on the “Second MR Invitation” (FarFish, D3.6), where the OTs for the CS5 were set. The focus of the MR1 was the black hake and shrimp fishery, but in MR2, the focus is on the black hake and pelagic fisheries. In MR2, the shrimp fishery was not included, despite it being mentioned in the “Second MR invitation” (FarFish, D3.6). This is due to little interest among operators, due to the declining catches and increased effort, due to closures of fishing grounds for the EU fleet. MR2 aims to improve the quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the SFPA and strive to provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches and bycatch.

7.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendation

A. Analysis of the MR Implementation

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. To conduct this task successfully, an audit of the management recommendations is carried out for each case study. This stage is broken down into two phases: a documentation system conformance analysis (A.1) and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

For MR2, the documentation system conformance is audited based on the results from the first audit of MR1 (FarFish D5.1), referring to the relevant documentation for developing the second MR, namely the “General Guidelines for making MRs” (FarFish, D3.5) and the “Second MR Invitation” (FarFish, D3.6). The auditor will assess whether there are any changes (positive or negative), based on evidence presented in MR2.

AUTHORITIES

The role of the authority is taken by MATIS in WP3 of the FarFish project. MR2 states that they should consider input from the competent authorities, e.g. Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy (MPEM), the Management of Oceanic Resources (DARE), the National Office for Fisheries and Aquaculture Inspection (ONISPA), the Management of Industrial Fishing (DPI), IMROP, and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). MR2 presents additional consulting authorities in comparison to MR1. These are ONISPA, DPI and IMROP. These added consulting

institutions are considered as a positive change in MR2 and decrease the risk highlighted by the auditors in the MR1 audit, of having a research institution as the representative authority. This risk stated that the partners involved in MR1, may not sufficiently reflect the reality and expectation of the acted authority. This risk has been tackled adequately. The auditor highlights in particular the participation of IMROP as the official Mauritanian fisheries research centre, which holds a fundamental role in MR2 as CS leader. Furthermore, MR2 presents evidence of active engagement of this entity in section 1.4.1. However, the auditors consider that the participation of the other authorities was not clearly elaborated in the MR2 and suggests providing more detailed description of the engagement from the consulting authorities in subsequent documents.

OPERATOR

MR2 reports no changes or additions in the partner operators involved. UiT holds the role of the operator within the FarFish project, and the European operator qualified to respond to the MR Invitation are the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR). The auditors highlight the active role that these operators took in implementing the actions defined for the OT5.1, 5.2 and 5.5 and the continuous effort to ensure contact with relevant operators through different workshops organized by WP1 and mentioned in section 1.4. However, the auditor considers that the recommendations provided in the MR1 audit were not sufficiently addressed in terms of participation. MR2 does not mention the list of active vessels operating in Mauritania for the relevant categories, which is fundamental to establish a baseline of participation in the MR2. Furthermore, there is no mention of any specific action to include other relevant fleets in the MR2 activities, which would strengthen the document. A more active involvement of the Pelagic Freezer-trawler Association (FPA), as well as efforts towards involving the local fleet, would have been desirable as suggested in MR1 audit. The auditors recognize that MR2 reports that they currently have no operation in Mauritanian waters. However, their input would have been valuable. Nevertheless, the auditor acknowledges that due to the scope of the action within the FarFish project the represented operators ensure sufficient participation of the EU fleet in Mauritania.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

The aim of the second version of the MR is divided in two main components, first to improve the quality of the stock assessment for the species included in the SFPA and second, to strive to provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches and bycatch. The definition of the aim has been expanded as it was planned in MR1, where the improvement of knowledge on the two black hake species was prioritized. Including small pelagics into the Mauritanian CS is of relevance, considering the key role of this fishery within the SFPA, for other fleets and, for Mauritania as well. The FarFish project has mentioned in several documents (D2.1, D3.4, D3.6, D5.2 and D5.3) the importance of the small pelagics as a resource, the vulnerability of its state and the uncertainties around the catch reporting and stock assessment. By including this category in the aim of MR2, the document is in line

with the reported priorities of the CS and fulfils the agreement made within the operators and authorities in MR1.

Regarding black hake fisheries, the auditors emphasised in MR1 the importance of striving for the participation from other fleets targeting these species, including the local fleet, in the project's actions. Also, in MR1 coordinating actions with Senegal were encouraged, as the two countries share the black hake resource, alongside with further involvement of other regional partners from CECAF, such as Morocco and The Gambia. MR2 mentions that the operators are aware of the OTs related to black hake should be taken as a coordinated regional action. However, it is mentioned that is beyond the scope of the FarFish project. Further, MR2 mentions that CECAF and FAO are implementing a regional approach. This acknowledgement of the need for regional coordination and consideration of other relevant actions by CECAF and FAO, satisfies the auditors comments in this regard.

OUTCOME TARGETS AND INDICATORS

Indicators and strategies have been revised in the MR2, compared to MR1 Audit. The auditors analyse the relevance of the changes in this section.

A summary of the Management Objectives, OTs and indicators defined for the Mauritanian case is presented in Table 57.

Table 57 CS5 Mauritania: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators

Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Improve the quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided. Obligatory	I_1_CS5 Visual identification of black hake species from self-sampling - Indicator Cat. C I_2_CS5 Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C I_3_CS5 Molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. A I_4_CS5 Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires - Indicator Cat. A I_5_CS5 Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling - Indicator Cat. A
	OT 5.2 Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided. Obligatory	I_6_CS5 Sampling protocol and templates for data collection provided - Indicator Cat. C I_7_CS5 Training of skippers, crews, and observers in visual species identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. C

		<p>I_8_CS5 Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_9_CS5 Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C</p>
Increase and improve the data collection on bycatch and discard from high-capacity pelagic vessels	<p>OT 5.3 Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place. Obligatory</p>	<p>I_10_CS5 A specific protocol with well-described units for the observations available – Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_11_CS5 Number of vessels having onboard observers - Indicator Cat. B</p>
Gathering available fisheries data for catches, discards, and bycatches.	<p>OT 5.4 Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided. Recommended</p>	<p>I_12_CS5 Data on all catches available - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_13_CS5 Data on discards and bycatch available - Indicator Cat. C</p>
Improve knowledge in the value chain, processing, and market conditions	<p>OT 5.5 Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided. Recommended</p>	<p>I_14_CS5 Data on catch quantities and landing destination available - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_15_CS5 Data on processing and trade available - Indicator Cat. C</p> <p>I_16_CS5 Data on socio-economic variables available - Indicator Cat. C</p>

Several changes were reported in the description of the OTs from MR1 to MR2. They will hereby be audited.

OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided.

OT 5.1 was rephrased in MR2 to “information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided” whilst in MR1 the goal was to “estimate the proportion of *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis* into the catch composition”. Rephrasing this OT contributed to the SMART analysis by making the OT more specific, as it focuses on obtaining information rather than estimating a proportion. The OT continues to be relevant to the objective of improving the stock assessment, by providing additional information on the two black hake species in the catches.

The indicators defined for this OT 5.1 have not been changed substantially. However, during the first audit, important considerations were put forward. In particular, the indicator **I_1_CS5** was questioned in terms of assignability and relevance. In terms of assignability, the auditors mentioned the limited number of vessels involved in the visual identification action. In this regard, the auditors considered that some lessons could be drawn from the Senegalese CS into the Mauritanian CS. In the Senegalese CS, with a comparable OT 4.1 also on information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches, the first indicator in this OT focused on training of Senegalese observers, instead of focusing on the visual identification alone, as it is written in **I_1_CS5**. This phrasing of OT 4.1 and focus on

training of local observers, potentially contributed to have reached other relevant fleets, as trained scientific observers can serve in different vessels. Also, in terms of relevance, considering redirecting this indicator into a training for visual identification could have contributed to solve the need of supportive identification on port, that was suggested by the operator representative (OPROMAR) during MR1, as it would focus on training instead of the visual identification alone. Yet, the auditor acknowledges that the action was implemented successfully with the vessels from OPROMAR, which mitigates some of these concerns. Nevertheless, the auditors still encourage utilising synergies with the Senegalese CS.

Two more indicators were added to OT 5.1. These two indicators refer to the provision of feedback to operators and crew about the self-sampling results. The added indicators respond to the recommendation made in the MR1 audit, where the auditor suggested to ensure coordination, good communication and feedback on sample quality and results between operators and scientific institution. These communication protocols were included in I_4_CS5 “Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires” and I_5_CS5 “Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling”. As the latter two indicators are new in MR2, a SMART analysis is then required and presented in Table 58:

Table 58 SMART analysis for I_4_CS5 and I_5_CS5

Specific	Not clear. In text I_4_CS4 does not specify what feedback is required. The auditor assumes the purpose is to highlight issues related to implementing the self-sampling protocol by operators and crew. More clarity could be given in text. I_5_CS4 is more specific, and the purpose of the feedback is clearly stated
Measurable	I_4_CS4 . Yes, the category A entails that the indicators should provide the percentage of vessels doing identification that gives feedback in return. I_5_CS4 . Partially, what percentage is to be communicated? The percentage of crew and operators having returns from the molecular analysis or the percentage of satisfactory results from samples?
Assignable	Partly, yet, the entities in charge of the tasks are not stated
Relevant	Yes, the indicators satisfy the need to communicate results to participants in the program
Time	Partly, should follow the identification process

OT 5.2: Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided

OT 5.2 was rephrased to “Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided”, compared to “collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters”. Considering the SMART framework, rephrasing the OT has made it more specific as it focuses on the provision of information, rather than data collection. Yet, by removing the text “by all operators in Mauritanian

waters” the OT is now less assignable. According to the MR2, the auditor implies that the provision of information on black hake bycatch is mostly expected from the fleet targeting small pelagic species. Yet this is not clarified in the OT text. The auditors suggest specifying the text of the OT the targeted fleet which should provide the bycatch information. On the topic of assignability, it is important to acknowledge that in the first audit, this OT had the critical challenge of ensuring participation of all operators and then, the auditors suggested to be more specific on the level of engagement and participation in the sampling program. The rephrasing of the OT takes into consideration this recommendation and better reflects that the participation in the program is indeed voluntary. Yet the need to specify that the bycatch data is expected from the fleet targeting small pelagic species, remains.

The indicators to measure the performance of OT 5.2 have significantly changed. The first indicator I_6_CS5 is new in MR2 and aims for the “sampling protocol and templates for data collection provided”, the indicator will be measured with the binary category C. This new indicator should be audited through the SMART analysis in Table 59:

Table 59 SMART analysis for I_6_CS5

Specific	Yes, the indicator clearly described the documents to be provided
Measurable	Yes, the documents to provide are indicated in text
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 section 5.4.1
Relevant	Yes, the documents serve the purpose of providing information on bycatches
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the documents are provided

The other three indicators for OT5.2 have been rephrased, although the nature of the action remains. Indicator I_7_CS5 is now defined as “Training of skippers, crews, and observers in visual species identification of black hake” previously in MR1, the indicators were only assignable to skippers and crew. In MR2 observers are now included in the training, which makes the indicator more relevant while remaining measurable. Yet, although the auditor suggested to score this indicator through a more quantitative category, like A, this was not taken upon. The auditors question this decision as the number of participants to the training programs should be known. The performance audit will assess this situation further. The last two indicators refer to the implementation of the training though the visual identification of the subsamples of black hake as bycatch in I_8_CS5 and the collection of fin samples for molecular analysis in I_9_CS5. The indicator that aimed to conducting the preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake was dropped, this signalizes to the auditors that the molecular analysis was not carried out and that therefore, the OT was not fully implemented. This will be elaborated in the performance audit in section B.

OT 5.3: Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place

OT5.3 was also rephrased from “Full onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels” to “Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place”. This OT was numbered 5.6 in MR1, where it stated that it was going to be developed in MR2. Therefore, no MR1 audit was conducted for this OT, as it was not fully elaborated. OT5.3 is obligatory in MR2. Rephrasing of the OT5.3 reflects the interactions between authorities and operators’ representatives within the FarFish project. Since, it was reported that in the meeting carried out in Marrakech in 2019, it was indicated that striving for full observer coverages was outside of the FarFish project’s capacity and instead, the OT should aim to increase the current observer coverage to high-capacity pelagic vessels. The auditors consider that the updated text is in line with the results from this meeting.

Two indicators were defined for this OT5.3 as described in Table 4. The first indicator I_10_CS strives for “a specific protocol with well-described units for the observations available” and the second, I_11_CS5 aims to determine the “number of vessels having onboard observers”. The SMART analysis for these indicators will be conducted in Table 60:

Table 60 SMART analysis for I_10_CS “A specific protocol with well-described units for the observations available”

Specific	Yes, the indicator specifies the protocol and content to be available
Measurable	Yes, it provides the units to describe in the protocol
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 section 5.5.1
Relevant	Yes, the protocol contributes to the OT objective stated in
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the protocol is available

The second indicator I_11_CS5 aims to determine the “number of vessels having onboard observers”. The auditors acknowledge the implementation of the suggestion from the Mauritanian CS leader, about measuring the achievement of the indicator I_11_CS5 through the indicator category B, which contributes to the measurability of the indicator. The SMART analysis is done in Table 61.

Table 61 SMART analysis for I_11_CS “Number of vessels having onboard observers”

Specific	Yes, the indicator clearly states what to measure
Measurable	Partly, the OT is relevant for all high-capacity pelagic vessels in Mauritania, should clarify it in the text of the indicator
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 section 5.5.1
Relevant	Yes, this number serves to measure whether the OT objective was achieved
Timely	Partly, not clear whether the action needs to be periodic or only once

OT 5.4: Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided

This OT is a compilation of the recommended OTs 5.3, 5.4, and 5.5 described in MR1. These OT aimed to increase knowledge and data collection for black hake, shrimp and small pelagics. Following the results of the several interactions between operators and authorities, this OT was decided to focus on small pelagic species. In MR1, all these OTs were to be developed in MR, therefore there's no first audit for them. For OT5.4 two indicators were defined in MR2. I_12_CS5 states "data on all catches available" and I_13_CS5 "data on discards and bycatch available". The SMART analysis for these indicators will be conducted hereby in Table 62:

Table 62 SMART analysis for I_12_CS "Data on all catches available"

Specific	Partly, the indicator refers to data on catches, but it doesn't state in text that it is for small pelagic
Measurable	Partly, it does not specify that data on catches should be for small pelagic species
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.6.1
Relevant	Yes, the provision of this data contributes to the OT objective
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is provided

The second indicator I_13_CS5 aims for "Data on discards and bycatch available", this indicator has a similar SMART analysis to the I_12_CS5, where the main issue found is the lack of mention that the data should be on small pelagic species. The auditor recommends state in the text of the OT that the aim is to provide data on catch, bycatch and discards only for small species. The SMART analysis of I_13_CS5 is in Table 63.

Table 63 SMART analysis for I_13_CS "Data on discards and bycatch available"

Specific	Partly, the indicator refers to data on discards and bycatches, but it doesn't state in text that it is for small pelagic species
Measurable	Partly, it does not specify that data on discards and bycatches should be for small pelagic species
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.6.1
Relevant	Yes, the provision of this data contributes to the OT objective
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is provided

OT 5.5: Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided

This OT was described in MR1 as OT5.7 and aimed to "increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets fishing for small pelagic species on trade flows". In MR2, the OT was renumbered to OT5.5 and rephrased to "trade flow data on small pelagic species provided". This OT was not audited in MR1 as it was stated that it would be elaborated in MR2. The OT aims to continue monitoring and enabling

data collection for small pelagic beyond their landing. It incorporates one of the potential actions suggested in MR1 to analyse the “socio-economic effects and conditions linked to small pelagic species, e.g. employment, human consumption, and value”. There are three indicators defined for this OT. First, I_14_CS5 is about “data on catch quantities and landing destination available”, I_15_CS5 is on “data on processing and trade available” and I_16_CS5 is about “data on socio-economic variables available”. These indicators will be analysed through the SMART framework.

First, the I_14_CS5 refers to “data on catch quantities and landing destination available”, the SMART analysis is elaborated in Table 44. The relevance of the OT5.5. should be considered, as data on small pelagic catches is required in I_12_CS5 for OT5.4. The data already provided in OT5.4 should be considered, to avoiding unnecessary use of resources. The auditor recommends evaluating whether the data to collect for I_14_CS5 should then focus only on landing destinations. Table 64 presents the SMART analysis for this indicator.

Table 64 SMART analysis for I_14_CS

Specific	Yes, the indicator refers to data on catches and landing destination for small pelagics, which is in the OT text.
Measurable	Yes, two layers of data are described, first on catches and then on landing destination of small pelagic
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.7.1
Relevant	Partly, it adds knowledge to trade-flows. However, it should be noted that data on catches for small pelagic is also provided for in I_12_CS5 for OT5.4, and it should be used to avoid unnecessary use of resources
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is available. A deadline for this was written in MR2.

The second indicator I_15_CS5 aims for “Data on processing and trade available”. This indicator has a similar SMART analysis to the I_14_CS5, but it focuses on processing and trade. Considering the SMART analysis from this indicator in Table 65 and also, for indicator I_14_CS5 in Table 64, the auditor suggests evaluating the potential of integrating the two indicators. One indicator that states that data on landing destinations, processing, and trade on small pelagic is available. Integrating these two indicators into one would contribute to a more specific and relevant outcome, as well as adding efficiency to the reporting and audit process.

Table 65 SMART analysis for I_15_CS5

Specific	Yes, the indicator refers to data on processing and trade for small pelagic, as stated in the OT
Measurable	Partly, it clearly states the data needed, yet it is not clear which quantitative indicators will be considered.
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.6.1.
Relevant	Yes, the provision of this data contributes to the OT objective
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is provided. A deadline for this was written in MR2.

The third and last indicator is I_16_CS5 is about “data on socio-economic variables available”. The SMART analysis found that the indicator is too broad, and it should be narrowed down. Currently, the indicator implies that socio-economic variables will be available, which could mean that all the variables should be calculated. The auditor suggests updating the text of the indicator to “selected or main socio-economic indicators”. The SMART analysis is presented in Table 66.

Table 66 SMART analysis for I_16_CS “Data on socio-economic variables available”

Specific	Partly, the indicator refers to economic variables, yet it does not state which. This makes the indicator too broad. Consider writing selected or main socio-economic variables to narrow it down.
Measurable	Partly, it is clear it aims to provide economic variables, but is not specific enough to ensure measurability
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.6.1
Relevant	Yes, the provision of this data contributes to the OT objective
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is provided. A deadline for this was written in MR2.

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since the only OT addressing economic issues is OT5.5 on Trade flow data provided, most of the actions defined for this OT consists of building the data itself, therefore no baseline data is available. Hence, it is not relevant to conduct a sensitivity analysis.

B. Summary Documentation System Conformance Audit

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 67 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 81.

Table 67 CS5 Mauritania: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.	
Outcome Target	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided	The material, samplings protocols and templates developed are in line with the OT. Also, the reports results from the sample analysis conducted, reflect that the collected data was in line with the selected indicators.			
OT 5.2: Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided	The training material, samplings protocols and templates are in line with the OT. However, MR2 reports that not sufficient data has been collected. The need to strive for more active participation from the targeted fleet is needed to ensure that sufficient data will be obtained to fulfil the indicators.			
OT 5.3: Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place	Sufficient data was collected to meet with indicator I_10_CS5. However, challenges were reported in obtaining data for I_11_CS5, with low observer coverage information.			
OT 5.4: Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided	Sufficient data was collected to meet with indicator I_12_CS5, from public sources with high to medium agreement and medium to robust evidence. However, challenges were reported in obtaining data for I_13_CS5.			
OT 5.5: Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided	MR2 reports that data has been collected from public sources and will continue to collect primary data for the selected indicators. Results from the SMART analysis question the specificity and measurability of the indicators, these issues should be addressed to ensure the data collected meet the indicators needs.			

C. Analysis of the MR performance and adaptation

This stage of the audit determines the accuracy of the OTs assessing the effectiveness, compliance, and effects of the MR. The RBM states that the MR performance audit should be conducted periodically. At this stage, as stated in the Audit Framework for RBM⁷ “the auditor assesses whether or not (or the extent to which) the outcome targets are achieved. The auditor should provide updated information about implemented management actions and their apparent consequences⁸. For the operator, this assessment will provide a basis for continue drafting modified Management Recommendations (MR). For the authority, the assessment may be a basis for implementing sanctions or set conditions (if outcome targets were not achieved), for rewarding achievements, or for revising outcome targets”.

This stage is broken down in three phases: Effectiveness performance, Compliance and MR effects.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

The Auditor should receive evidence about achievement (or not) of the OTs and demonstrate the success or failure to perform the management goals. This analysis will be conducted for each of the defined OTs, with focus on analysing the achievement of each of the indicators:

OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided

To verify the performance of OT5.1, the operator has agreed upon five indicators as shown in Table 57. The performance assessment will be carried out for each of these indicators in Table 68.

Table 68 OT 5.1 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>ER Score</i>
<i>I_1_CS5</i> Visual identification of black hake species from self-sampling - <i>Indicator Cat. C</i>	MR2 reports on successful collection of visual reports from the crew on board three trawlers from OPROMAR. The MR2 reports that the crew collected the samples following the sampling protocol and recorded the data on the data sheets provided.	5
<i>I_2_CS5</i> Collection of fin samples of black hake for	Like the analysis of <i>I_1_CS5</i> , the crew from the three trawlers successfully collected the samples following the given protocols.	5

⁷ EcoFishMan Deliverable 4.4, p.8

⁸ In practice, the effects of management actions may not be directly observed, as this will depend on the type of management measures used as well as the type and quality of the collected information.

molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C		
I_3_CS5 Molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. A	MR2 reports that all the collected samples were processed, and the percentage of mislabelling is known.	5
I_4_CS5 Feedback provided from operators and crew via questionnaires - Indicator Cat. A	In section 5.3.2. of the MR2 states that I_4_CS5 depends on the willingness of the operators and crew to answer the questionnaires. However, the work from WP1 on stakeholder interaction minimizes the risk of not obtaining the feedback.	3
I_5_CS5 Feedback is given to operators and crew about the results from the self-sampling - Indicator Cat. A	Indicator I_5_CS5 will be achieved when the questionnaires' and self-sampling result is given to the operators and crews. This Indicator depends on the results from I_4_CS5 .	3
ER Score		4

OT 5.2: Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided

The performance evaluation of OT 5.2 is presented in Table 69. This OT performance was mostly affected by the lack of participation of non-EU fleet targeting small pelagic species in Mauritania. As mentioned in the implementation audit, the molecular analysis indicator was dropped due to the lack of sampling in the targeted fleet. The Senegalese CS showed case the potential positive results from implementing this OT for obtaining bycatch data by involving non-EU fleet. Collaboration and communication between Mauritania and Senegal are encouraged, to better utilize the resources developed within the project to implement the actions and advance in achieving this OT, even after the lifetime of the FarFish project.

Table 69 OT 5.2 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_6_CS5 Sampling protocol and templates for data collection provided - Indicator Cat. C	The materials produced for OT5.1 were available for OT5.2. This material could be implemented by the fleets targeting small pelagic species to report on black hake bycatch. Therefore, the materials are provided, and the resources developed in the project were efficiently utilized.	5
I_7_CS5 Training of skippers, crews, and observers in visual species identification of black hake - Indicator Cat. C	Although training materials are available, the fleet targeting small pelagic species is composed by non-EU vessels, which decreased participation. Authorities of the vessel's flag state or other entity must be involved to achieve this indicator. The Senegalese CS was mentioned as a blueprint for the potential positive results from implementing this action. Collaboration	3

	between the two Coastal States is encouraged to implement the training materials and protocols developed within the FarFish project.	
I_8_CS5 Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species - Indicator Cat. C	Like the analysis of I_7_CS5 . Authorities of the vessel's flag state or other entity must be involved to achieve this indicator. Collaboration with Senegalese partners is encouraged.	2
I_9_CS5 Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis - Indicator Cat. C	Like the analysis of I_7_CS5 and I_8_CS5 . Authorities of the vessel's flag state or other entity must be involved to achieve this indicator. Collaboration with Senegalese partners is encouraged.	2
ER Score		3

OT 5.3: Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place

For the OT 5.3, the effectiveness performance report is provided in Table 70. This OT was also mostly affected by effective collaboration with the Coastal State in terms of information exchange and potentially coordination. The FarFish project developed a specific protocol describing the units for observations, which could be implemented when the corresponding authorities from the Coastal State adopt them in collaboration with the operators. The protocol is a step forward for increasing observer coverage, yet several important actions are still pending to ensure that the OT is implemented and achieved.

Table 70 OT 5.3 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>ER Score</i>
I_10_CS5 A specific protocol with well-described units for the observations available – Indicator Cat. C	The protocol specified for this indicator was produced, however MR2 reports that implementing it requires collaboration of the operators and funding for training of observers, which is out of the scope of project. The protocol does contribute to the observer program if implemented, yet it would not be effective if not implemented.	4
I_11_CS5 Number of vessels having onboard observers - Indicator Cat. B	MR2 reports that accessing information about actual observer coverage in Mauritania has not been possible, which also impedes the quantitative estimation required for this indicator. Yet, MR2 presents information on the system established in the SFPAs and about other international projects dealing with the topic. Additional efforts are needed to collaborate with local authorities to ensure that observer coverage is better documented.	2
ER Score		3

OT 5.4: Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided

The effectiveness performance for OT5.4 is presented in Table 71. MR2 provides a comprehensive report on the catch data obtained and published in deliverable 2.1 by FarFish partner Université Cadi Ayyad (UCA) in Morocco. Yet some challenges remain in obtaining bycatch data, which are mostly associated with the lack of robust monitoring scheme in Mauritania. The performance of this indicator could benefit from implementing OT 5.2 and OT 5.4, which are also facing challenges related to collaboration from operators and local authorities. Coordinated action to implement these OT could render improvements in multiple areas (e.g. onboard observer coverage, data on bycatch and discards) which would enhance the monitoring of the fishing activities in the Mauritanian EEZ.

Table 71 OT 5.4 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_12_CS5 Data on all catches available - Indicator Cat. C	Data on all catches was provided from the FarFish deliverable 2.10 on data collected on small pelagic species and environmental forcing on the west coast of Africa from the Université Cadi Ayyad (UCA) in Morocco, delivered in December 2020. This report shows progress regarding data compilation for small pelagic species in Mauritania. However, uncertainty in the data provided is reported with high to medium agreement and medium to robust evidence.	5
I_13_CS5 Data on discards and bycatch available - Indicator Cat. C	The data on discards and bycatch are not available as the area lacks a robust monitoring scheme. MR2 reports only few studies published with quantitative data on discards and bycatch. Additional efforts are needed to promote monitoring and data collection.	3
ER Score		4

OT 5.5: Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided

MR2 reports that the work towards the provision of the trade flow data is ongoing and will be delivered within the lifetime of the FarFish project. The performance report for OT 5.5 is presented in Table 72.

Table 72 OT 5.5 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_14_CS5 Data on catch quantities and landing destination available - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 reports that some these data have already been reported in the document FarFish D3.4. Also reports that the data sources are the Joint Scientific Committee (JSC) and DG-Mare, supplemented with interviews to key Mauritanian informants. Additional reports on this data are expected at the end of the project.	4

I_15_CS5 Data on processing and trade available - Indicator Cat. C	Like the analysis of I_14_CS5 , Information about processing and trade of the raw materials originating from the EU SFPA small pelagic fishery is partly provided in D3.4 and will be expanded in a document at the end of the project. Some difficulties are reported in following the raw data into official statistics sources. However, this will be tackled by coupling the data from databases such as Global Fishing Watch with information from the processors and other key informants in Mauritania.	4
I_16_CS5 Data on socio-economic variables available - Indicator Cat. C	MR2 reports that socio-economic data like revenue, profitability, and value creation are not directly available. The aim is to obtain data through interviews or be estimated based on data from other sources. From the SMART analysis made above, the indicator is not specific and should be narrowed down to selected indicators, which will also ensure performance even with data constraints.	3
ER Score		3,7

C.2 Compliance

This item of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. A compliance assessment determines whether the specified criterion for the defined outcome target is met. This assessment includes a qualitative and quantitative analysis of completeness, timeliness, and quality of the sources of each indicator. The summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (CI) that will be reported in the audit summary.

OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided

OT 5.1 for CS5 Mauritania refers to the provision of information on the proportion of two species of black hake in catches. The MR2 reports that the OT was implemented by three EU trawlers. The compliance evaluation presented in Table 73 is done considering the actual participation reported in MR2 and the main challenges referring to participation of other relevant fleets.

Table 73 OT 5.1 Compliance evaluation and CI score

<i>Analysis</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>CI Score</i>
<i>Completeness Level (C)</i>	The key activities were described in section 5.3 of the MR2 were performed or are reported to be ongoing. The self-sampling protocol was provided, samples were taken and analysed in the laboratory. Results of these are available in MR2. Feedback from and to operators is pending.	4

Timeliness Level (T)	Results from the self-sampling protocol were provided in MR2. Feedback is expected to come before the project ends.	4
Source quality Level (S)	The samples were taken by three trawlers from OPROMAR operating in Mauritania. The analysis was made in the University of Oviedo. Promoting participation from other fleets is encouraged.	4
Total CI Score		4

OT 5.2: Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided

For OT 5.2, on information on black hake bycatch, the MR2 report that the targeted fleets are non-EU, which represent a major challenge in terms of participation in the program. The FarFish project is developing material that could be implemented if cooperation with the fleet targeting small pelagic species is reached. The compliance report is provided in Table 74.

Table 74 OT 5.2 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Protocols and template are provided and ready for implementation. However, challenges relating to involvement of relevant participants to participate in this action impede further advancement with this action	3
Timeliness Level (T)	The material was produced in due time and could be implemented at any time, if taken upon by relevant parties. Yet, lack of participation threatens implementation during the life of the project	3
Source quality Level (S)	The protocols and template were provided by CCMAR and were implemented successfully in OT5.1. Lack of implementation due to participation impeded the evaluation of whether the protocols and templates could provide useful results.	3
Total CI Score		3

OT 5.3: Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place

The OT 5.3 refers to increasing onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels. This target is operationalized by developing a specific protocol with well-described units for the observers. This protocol is provided, yet MR2 reports the need for collaboration of the operators in the Mauritanian EEZ and funding for training of the observers. This is reported as outside of the project's scope. Based on the MR2 report, the compliance evaluation is provided in Table 75.

Table 75 OT 5.3 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	A specific protocol with well described units for the observations is available. Lack of information on observer coverage and risk of implementations are a threat for the completion of this OT.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	The protocol was produced, and it is available on due time. Implementation on the other hand will require additional actions to ensure continuity after the FarFish project	3
Source quality Level (S)	The protocol for observations was developed by CCMAR with reported knowledge on the scientific observer system described in the SFPA protocols and the reports from the JSC. Yet, lack of implementation does not allow for potential feedback and evaluation in practice.	4
Total CI Score		3

OT 5.4: Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided

MR2 provides detailed reporting of the data on catches but also, reports challenges in obtaining data on bycatch and discards. The compliance evaluation draws on the reported achievements and challenges for the OT 5.4 in Table 76.

Table 76 OT 5.4 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Catch data was collected and reported in MR2. Data on discards and bycatch is not sufficiently available, which reveals a knowledge gap that needs to be fulfilled by additional research, and the need of a more robust monitoring scheme in Mauritania, as reported in MR2.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	The catch data was provided in due time. The report on the lack of discards and bycatch data is provided in time but filling this knowledge gap is not likely in the lifetime of the project.	4
Source quality Level (S)	Catch data was compiled from a report from the Université Cadi Ayyad (UCA) in Morocco. Time series suitable for modelling were compiled from several sources, national and international, and fisheries dependent and independent research surveys. Time series of fishing efforts for Mauritania are not available. The data on discard and bycatches are partially available from DG-Mare with further reporting still pending.	4
Total CI Score		3

OT 5.5: Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided

OT 5.5 refers to the provision of trade flow data on small pelagic species in the Mauritanian EEZ. MR2 reports that work is ongoing, specifying the source of the data to obtain and collect and the timing for the report. The compliance evaluation is presented in Table 77.

Table 77 OT 5.5 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	MR2 reports that trade flow data on small pelagic is partly provided in a FarFish deliverable (3.4). An additional report will be provided before the end of the project. Additional information will be collected from publicly available sources and key informants.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	The report is scheduled to be provided before the end of the project	4
Source quality Level (S)	The data sources for catch and landings were listed in the minutes from the joint scientific committee meetings with IMROP and DG MARE data. This information has been supplemented with a list of key Mauritanian informants. Socio-economic data will be obtained through interviews or estimated from other sources.	4
Total CI Score		4

D. MR Effects

This item of the audit aims to evaluate the impact of the MR in monetary terms. A cost-benefit analysis of the MR should perform based on the available data provided in MR2. However, the MRs have not been designed to managing the fisheries, but rather focus on specific areas within the fisheries and its management that needed attention according to the dialogue of the parts within the RBM process. Therefore, due to data limitation and uncertainty, as well as the difficulties to ascertain and isolate other factors from the impacts of management measures, the analysis will be conducted in a more qualitative manner.

OT 5.1 Information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches provided

The implementing of a protocol to identify the proportion of the two species of black hake in the catches can imply the deployment of a complicated logistic, in terms of distributing training materials, collecting samples, and sending samples to analysis, which could lead to substantial costs. However,

these actions are considered beneficial for all stakeholders, as they could contribute to improve the knowledge on the status of the stocks and therefore, improve their management. The implemented methodology could be replicable in other case studies, as proven through the successful implementation of the action in the Senegalese CS4, which was also proven a cost-efficient method to attain the target to obtain information of the two black hake species. The MR effect analysis is summarized in Table 78.

Table 78 OT 5.1 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Direct costs associated	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Improved stocks knowledge	Benefit	Likely	RFMO, National administrations, Operators	Short-medium and long
Better resource management	Benefit & Cost	Likely	RFMO, National administrations, Operators	Short-medium and long
Capacity Building	Benefit	Uncertain		Short and medium

OT 5.2: Information on black hake caught as bycatch provided

Information on black hake bycatch from vessels targeting small pelagic species is scarce, therefore efforts to obtain more information is in general terms beneficial. The OT aimed to transfer the protocols developed in the self-sampling program, to be implemented by the relevant fleet, which is a cost-efficient use of resources produced under the FarFish project. Conducting self-sampling protocols on board these vessels will be beneficial for improving current stock assessment. Addition information, establishing a robust and replicable protocol for collecting observer’s data, as well as the training of observers is a positive step forward in the efficiency of the fishing process. However, participation and implementation appear as a fundamental challenge in this CS. Lack of participation could hamper the realization of the benefits from the resources already utilized for this OT. This analysis is summarized in Table 79.

Table 79 OT 5.2 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Direct costs associated to training	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Training and boarding observers	Cost	Medium	RFMOs, National administrations and operators	Medium and long
Bycatch are regulated	Cost	Small to medium	Operators	Short, medium, and long
Better resource management	Benefit	Highly uncertain	RFMOs, National administrations and operators	Medium to long
Improved capacity of observers' program	Benefit	Highly uncertain	RFMOs, National administrations and operators	Medium and long

OT 5.3: Increased onboard observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels in place

Observer coverage is reportedly low in Mauritania. As such, the need for increasing it is evident. There are significant costs in increasing coverage of an observer program with several reported limitations. However, as the OT5.3 is focused on high-capacity pelagic vessels, this narrows the scope and consequently the expected costs. Also, considering the need for increasing the coverage, the costs of implementation are likely to be compensated by the total value added from the fishery. Furthermore, the benefits from training observers and increasing the coverage can be transferred to other fleets. The question on who bears these costs of the program, depends how it is implemented – the costs could be levied to the fishing vessels themselves, taken by the authorities or shared between them. This action could have short-, medium-, and long-term impacts, although they are difficult to predict. In general terms, it is expected that better observer coverage and therefore better data collection, could lead to improvements in management of both target and bycatch stocks. This analysis is summarized in Table 80.

Table 80 OT 5.2 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Cost of observer programme	Cost	Small	To be defined. Likely authorities and vessels	All time scales
Yield implications from management measures	Benefit	Uncertain	Vessels, processors, and downstream actors	Medium- and long-term

OT 5.4: Data on all catches, discards and bycatches provided

The goal of this OT is to collect data on catch, bycatch, and discards of small pelagic species. This action aims to increase knowledge for the assessment of the small pelagic stocks, and therefore potentially improve the management of these fisheries. The costs related to data collection could be considered low and incurred, as catch reports were publicly available data and resources from project partners were utilized. However, the reported lack of bycatch and discards data could entail the need for additional research and data collection tasks that are costly. The development of Data Limited Tools for stock assessment contributes to narrowing this knowledge gap. The costs of developing these tools are considerable. However, they have been incurred by the FarFish project.

OT 5.5: Trade flow data on small pelagic species provided

The information gathered in this OT will be utilized for a cost-benefit analysis of the small pelagic fisheries in Mauritania, which will be published as part of the FarFish project. The more precise the information in this OT, the more precise this analysis will be, while the costs would be relatively low and incurred by the project. The investment potential is likely high, as a shared stock, the small pelagic industry is of significant relevance in terms of development and food security in West Africa.

7.3 Summary of the Audit

The audit dashboard is presented in Table 81. Overall, the MR2 for Mauritania is progressing in an adaptive manner. The developments from MR1 to MR2 reflect the interests of the involved operators. Some limitations were found in terms of participation, which hindered better implementation of some of the actions. The OT 5.1 about information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches has great potential for the implementation of a more regional approach in the management of the black hake stocks. Although the action is well advanced, the good performance in the Senegalese CS could be replicated in the Mauritanian CS, where broader participation could render important advancements. The OT 5.2 is also dependent on participation. Most of the resources to conduct the action have been developed in FarFish could be implemented, yet the non-EU fleet is outside of the scope of the project. For the OT 5.3, important advancements have been reported. However, lack of data is a critical challenge, and additional efforts to collaborate with the local authorities are needed to attain this goal. The OT 5.4 rendered important advancements in terms of data collection and evidenced the importance of collaborating at regional level, considering the data was analysed in Morocco. Challenges towards obtaining by-catch data remain. Additional efforts are needed towards increasing monitoring and data collection, which relates to OT 5.3. Finally, work towards achieving the

OT 5.5 on trade flow data is well advanced and the final report is expected within the lifetime of the FarFish project.

Table 81 Audit Dashboard: Summary of the evaluation of CS5 Mauritania MR2

PHASE			OT 5.1	OT 5.2	OT 5.3	OT 5.4	OT 5.5
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENTATION	Documentation system	Crit. 1					
	Documentation system	Crit. 2					
	Documentation system	Crit. 3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant					
Responsive Assessment							
Step 2 MR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER					
	Compliance Assessment	CI					
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Progress			On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment						
	Final assessment						

8 CS6: SFPA Seychelles

8.1 General remarks

The Management Recommendations (MR2) for the Seychelles SFPA fisheries was submitted on February 22nd, 2021. The audit process is thereafter initiated.

MR2 is a follow up report of performance from MR1 proposed for the EU tuna fishery in Seychelles waters. The tuna fishery in the Indian Ocean is governed by the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC). There are currently 31 contracting parties to IOTC, including the EU and Seychelles. The CS6 focuses on the EU fleet, yet several physical meetings to review ongoing work were held with administration, scientists, and stakeholders were representatives from Seychelles companies and fishing operators (purse seiner and artisanal fisheries) also attended meetings. The main objectives of the MR2 for Seychelles are to enhance the scientific knowledge base for managing these fisheries, minimise the lack of data to undertake stock assessments of bycatch species, and support the fight against IUU fishing.

8.2 Evaluation of the Management Recommendation

A. MR Implementation

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective evaluation based on a precise assemble of reliable information and applying adaptive management principles. To conduct this task successfully, an audit of the management recommendations is carried out for each case study. This stage is broken down in two phases: a documentation system conformance analysis (A.1) and a sensitivity analysis (A.2).

A.1 Documentation System Conformance

For MR2, the documentation system conformance is audited based on the results from the first audit of MR1 and an assessment has been conducted of whether there are any changes (positive or negative), based on evidence from MR2.

AUTHORITIES

For the Seychelles case the leading authority is Matis, with input from relevant authorities, e.g. SFA and DG MARE. Additional consulting authorities are included in MR2, e.g. FAO, CGPOP, and CAF, however some abbreviations are not provided (e.g. CGPOP) to assess relevance. Nevertheless, the auditors consider that authorities are representative for developing the MR2. Besides the input from the additional consulting organizations, no other changes are reported since MR1.

OPERATOR

The European operators qualified to respond to the MR2 Invitation will provide feedback through three designated stakeholder organisations: OPAGAC, ANFACO-CECOPECA, and LDAC. The leader of WP4, UiT, has assisted the representatives of operators in developing the MR2. The auditors consider that the operators included in the MR2 represent a main portion of the EU fishing interests in the Seychelles SFPFA fisheries.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MR2

The main goal of the Seychelles case MR2 is enhancing the scientific knowledge base, improve data for stock assessment of bycatch stocks and contribute to deter and eliminate IUU fishing. Management challenges in the fishery are well described in section 4 of MR2, which provide good justification for the relevance of the main goals selected.

OUTCOME TARGETS AND INDICATORS

Based on the revision of indicators and strategies in the MR2 for the Seychelles SFPFA fisheries, a new audit is conducted. The auditors also evaluate whether actions have been taken towards resolving the issues found in the audit of MR1.

A summary of the OTs and indicators defined for the CS of the Seychelles fisheries, indicating the management objectives they relate to, is presented in Table 82. The recommended OT6.4 from MR1 on the Provision of data on the use of FADs within Seychelles EEZ has been removed from M2 based on topic complexity and resource availability and considering that the topic is being tackled at the RFMO level by the CPC. All the other OT's have been rephrased and simplified.

The final selection of the OTs in MR2 are based on MR1, the results of the first audit of MR1 and further, results of the interactions in reported meetings facilitated by the FarFish project. The auditors consider that the provision of a short description about the information obtained through this process explaining the relevance of these OTs and how they link to the main goals could facilitate the evaluation of the MRs.

Table 82 Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators of CS SWA

Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Improving the scientific knowledge base for the fisheries management	OT 6.1 Harmonised fisheries information system in place. Obligatory	I_1_CS6 Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the SFPa agreement. - Indicator Cat. C I_2_CS6 Standardised fisheries information presented - Indicator Cat. B
	OT 6.2 Catches of non-target species registered in e-logbooks. Obligatory	I_3_CS6 Template for catch protocol for nontarget species to be implemented in e-logbooks - Indicator Cat. C I_4_CS6 Model implementation of DLM to bycatch species - Indicator Cat. B
Enhance a level playing field where all fleets comply by the commitment to honour Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)	OT 6.3 Marine Protected Area (MPAs) and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected. Obligatory	I_5_CS6 Operator compliance verified by analysis of VMS or AIS data for SMSP Initiative – Indicator Cat. C
Support the fight against IUU fishing by utilizing the latest available satellite system and tools	OT 6.4 Updated observer program in place. Recommended	I_6_CS6 Regional observer program in place - Indicator Cat. C I_7_CS6 Regional observer program implemented - Indicator Cat. C
Improve knowledge about the value chain and market conditions.	OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided. Recommended	I_8_CS6 Information on catch and landings provided - Indicator Cat. C I_9_CS6 Information on processing and trade provided - Indicator Cat. C I_10_CS6 Socio-economic impacts of using drifting FADs provided - Indicator Cat. C
Support the fight against IUU fishing by utilizing the latest satellite systems and tools	OT 6.6 Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) or Automatic Identification System (AIS) signals are transmitted. Recommended	I_9_CS6 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geolocalization - Indicator Cat. B I_10_CS6 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS), geolocalization - Indicator Cat. B

OT 6.1 *Harmonised fisheries information system in place. Obligatory*

This OT refers to the harmonization of fisheries information and aims to contribute towards the objective of “improving the scientific knowledge base for the fisheries management”, together with OT6.2 on the registration of catches in e-logbooks. Following the SMART analysis, **OT 6.1** continues to be relevant for this objective. Though, the auditors consider that rephrasing the OT has made it

somewhat less specific, in terms of what information systems are to be included and harmonised. Also, in terms of the assignability it is not stated who the beneficiaries of the harmonized system will be. The issues with specificity and assignability, further affect the measurability. Several of these concerns are clarified in the MR2 progress report for this OT6.1. The auditors suggests that the OT could be more precise if it is defined as a pilot project, as it is suggested in the MR2 section 5.3, where it states, “Develop a pilot project to create a harmonised fisheries information system with a single way of reporting catch and effort data text”. The auditors suggest considering rephrasing the OT to adjust it to increase consistency to need and progress reported in MR2.

In terms of the key activities and indicators, these are clear and relevant. However, the selected indicators do not provide a clear measurement for achievement of the OT, which as reported has measurability issues. Nevertheless, the specified activities are clearly relevant to identify gaps and suggest improvements. Yet they do not cover the actual implementation required to fulfil the OT. As to indicator I_2_CS6, it is not clear what the difference between a harmonised fisheries information system (the OT) and standardised fisheries information (I_2_CS6) is. These two terms were used extensively throughout the progress report, which increases the need for clarification of these concepts.

OT 6.2 Catches of non-target species registered in e-logbooks. Obligatory

The OT6.2 has been rephrased from “development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks” to “catches of non-target species registered in e-logbooks”. As mentioned, this OT is relevant for the objective of improving scientific knowledge for fisheries management. From the MR1 audit, this OT reported issues with measurability and specificity. By rephrasing the OT, the auditor considers it has improved specificity and relevance, however it could improve its measurability if the non-target species were specified. Also, in terms of assignability, the MR2 assigns responsibility for indicators, but not to the OT, which is considered a shortcoming. The timeframe for the objective has not been specified but is assumed to be within the FarFish project’s lifetime.

In terms of indicators, I_3_CS6 remains unchanged and I_4_CS6 is new. Indicator I_3_CS6 is considered specific, measurable, and relevant for the objective. However, it is worth noting, that the indicator is relevant for fisheries in Seychelles. Yet the lack of data on bycatch species is a much wider problem in the Indian ocean, which requires more coordinated action at the international level. Furthermore, the indicator continues to have issues with assignability, as it is mentioned in MR2 that this activity will make more sense if it was assigned to all fleets licensed to fish in the Seychelles EEZ. However, this goes beyond the scope of FarFish.

The second indicator I_4_CS6, is included to conduct the key activity to explore data-limited methods (DLM) applied to data available for non-target species. As this indicator is recently added to OT6.2, it is subject to the SMART analysis, as presented in Table 83.

Table 83 SMART analysis indicator I_4_CS6

Specific	Partly. The indicator mentions a model implementation of DLM tools. Yet it does not state for what purpose. It should state in text that the model is implemented for stock status estimation.
Measurable	Partly. The indicator should state for how many species will the DLM be implemented, to measure achievement. MR2 states that at least two species were modelled and therefore not fully achieved.
Assignable	Yes, the responsible party is stated in MR2 in section 5.4.1
Relevant	Partly. This indicator refers to the objective (and second key activity), but it is not necessarily relevant for the OT itself, this link should be better justified.
Timely	Yes, the action ends when the data is provided. A deadline for this was written in MR2.

OT 6.3 MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected. *Obligatory*

OT6.3 was rephrased from “Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP” to “MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected”. This OT relates directly to the main objective of enhancing level playing field through compliance of all fleet to the commitment to honour MPA’s. MR2 states that the key activity for achieving this indicator is analysing VMS or AIS data to verify operators' compliance to honour MPAs. The auditors consider that the use of the word “verify” is not adequate in this setting, as the potential results from this analysis could be also non-compliance. The auditors team suggest revising the wording and consider using other words (e.g. check, assess, evaluate) instead. The Indicator I_5_CS has been slightly reworded from “Operator compliance” to “Operator compliance verified by analysis of VMS or AIS data for SMSP Initiative”. This partly addresses the issues mentioned by the auditor during MR1, in terms of data sources as challenges to obtaining VMS data were mentioned in MR1. Rephrasing the indicator has made it more specific. The indicator continues to be relevant and measurable, but in terms of assignability, it is not clear for whom the report from the analysis will be presented. The suggested indicator is limited to measure the compliance itself and does not provide any indications on additional actions towards achieving the objective as such.

OT 6.4 Updated observer program in place. *Recommended*

This OT is formulated to respond to the objective of supporting the fight against IUU fishing by utilizing the latest satellite systems and tools. The OT was rephrasing from “setting of conditions for a better coordination of observer programme: content (protocol criteria) schedules, processes, sharing

information” to “Updated observer program in place”. Three key activities are defined, which are clear, but rather ambitious. MR2 describes that both the scientific and compliance observer program should be updated, and that this should have a regional scope. The auditors consider that stating these in the OT description would have contributed to its evaluation. For OT 6.4, two indicators have been defined I_6_CS6 and I_7_CS6, referring to a regional observer program to be in place and then to be implemented, respectively. As it is now, the text of the OT is somewhat disconnected to the indicators and should be revised. The OT should clearly state the goal of updating the scientific and compliance observer program with a regional scope.

Furthermore, comparing the text of the OT “updated observer program in place” and of the indicator I_6_CS6 “regional observer program in place”, the wording should be revised as they are too similar. Also, the wording in the OT and indicators should be more concise, utilising similar concepts, i.e. state that the aim is either to create a regional observer program, or to update and existing observer program and expand it to the regional level. The SMART analysis for these indicators is presented in Table 84.

Table 84 SMART analysis for indicators I_6_CS6 and I_7_CS6

Specific	Partly, both I_6_CS6 and I_7_CS6 have a clear purpose, yet it lacks to specify whether the observer program is scientific or for compliance check
Measurable	Yes. Both indicators indicate which level of implementations is expected
Assignable	Partly, responsible parties are mentioned as examples in MR2 in section 5.6.1. However, not clear who will take charge of the activities and by whom will the program be designed
Relevant	Partly. MR2 mentions that both the scientific and compliance observer program should be updated and have regional scope. Improving the specificity of the indicators in would contribute to the relevance
Timely	No. It is not clear when the outcome is expected

OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided. Recommended

This OT refers to the provision of trade flow data. This OT was previously a recommended action and suggested the “mandatory provision of sales invoices (sales certificates) in order to verify the markets in which tuna derived from Seychelles EEZ appears (e.g. canning or others)”. Rephrasing this OT has made it more attainable, as I was highly unlikely to obtain such documentation from tuna processors. The provision of trade flow data is a relevant action towards the goal of improving knowledge about the value chain and market conditions. In terms of the SMART analysis, the OT could be more specific by providing more detail in terms of which species, processing types, trade variables, etc, will be provided. An additional level of detail would further allow for better measurability. In terms of the defined indicators, the first two (I_8_CS6 and I_9_CS6) refer to the provision of information of catch and landings, and processing and trade. These indicators contribute to the goal of the OT. However,

the indicator I_10_CS6 on the “Socio-economic impacts of using drifting FADs provided” is questioned by the auditors in terms of its relevance against the OT itself and further justification is needed for this.

OT 6.6 VMS or AIS signals are transmitted. Recommended

This OT has been slightly rephrased, yet the nature of the OT remains. The OT has been formulated to support the fight against IUU fishing by use of new electronic and satellite systems. The activity to achieve this target is to explore ideas on monitoring of fisheries in MPAs applying new methods and tools. The OT has relevance to the overall aim of reducing IUU fisheries and challenges within the fishery. The OT is measurable and well specified. This also applies to the selected indicators. However, none of them are explicitly assigned to a responsible body, neither given a clear timeframe in MR2.

The auditors consider that the link between the OT and key activities is not clearly defined in MR2. In comparison with other case studies, where an OT of similar characteristics was defined, this link was clearer as the target was to develop a big-data analysis of AIS and VIIRS-DNB, which should then be used to conduct an analysis of the correspondence between VMS and AIS data in the selected fisheries. This is not defined in the Seychelles CS. Also, it is not specified to what degree any activity taking place to achieve OT6.6 will contribute to a higher level of transmission of VMS and/or AIS data.

Finally, the auditors found that the OT6.6, as described in the MR2 overlaps with OT6.3. This is clarified in the text of MR2, stating that OT6.3 is to use VMS and AIS to verify operators’ compliance to honour MPAs. However, for OT6.6 one of the key activities described in section 5.8 is to “explore ideas on monitoring of fisheries in MPAs applying new methods and tools”. This activity, in the opinion of this auditor team, creates an overlap, making the OTs too similar. The auditors suggest revising further and coordinating of the activities planned for each of these OTs to potentially merging them into one OT.

A.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since the only OT addressing economic issues is OT6.5 on trade flow data provided, which focuses the effort on obtaining and building the data from primary sources. No baseline data is available, it is therefore not relevant to conduct a sensitivity analysis.

B. Summary of Documentation System Conformance

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 85. The audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 103.

Table 85 CS6 Seychelles: Summary of audit results of the documentation system audit for MR2

Outcome Target	CRITERIA 1. The available data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program	
	Evidence-base		Evidence-base	
OT 6.1 <i>Harmonised fisheries information system in place.</i> Obligatory	MR2 states that a report has been delivered, that indicates meeting data requirements to achieve indicator I_1_CS6. Also, data were collected that would enable fulfilling of indicator I_2_CS6. Issues with OT concept and the definitions of harmonization and standardisations should be revised.			
OT 6.2 <i>Catches of non-target species registered in e-logbooks.</i> Obligatory	Relevant data have been collected against two selected species concerning indicator I_4_CS6. Yet, the main challenge to obtain data remains as E-logbooks are not implemented in Seychelles.			
OT 6.3 <i>MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected.</i> Obligatory	Progress was made in designating areas for implementation. Yet it was specified that VMS and AIS data should be collected. Data have so far not been available due to data restrictions. Fundamental data is lacking to conduct the analysis.			
OT 6.4 <i>Updated observer program in place.</i> Recommended	No data are specified to be collected to measure the selected indicators. However, the indicators are of a binomial nature that is relatively easy to assess.			

	CRITERIA 1. The available data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program	
<p>OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided. Recommended</p>	<p>Data on catches and landings are collected, meeting indicator I_8_CS6. Processing and trade data are being collected but has not been completed yet. A questionnaire is planned to obtain information contributing to indicator I_10_CS6. This would provide some relevant information, but likely only partially fulfil the indicator.</p>			
<p>OT 6.6 VMS or AIS signals are transmitted. Recommended</p>	<p>Methodology is not described in MR2, but in a separate report. Access to VMS data were requested but could not be shared with FarFish due to legal restraints. AIS data were not transmitted due to security/piracy considerations. Hence, efforts to collect data were made, but were not available. Considering merging OT6.3 and OT6.6 to focus efforts and resources for continuing striving for obtaining data for achieving the target.</p>			

C. MR Audit and adaptation

The RBM proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for such responsiveness. There are two phases to support this stage, effectiveness performance and compliance evaluation.

C.1 Effectiveness Performance

OT 6.1 *Harmonised fisheries information system in place. Obligatory*

For the OT 6.1 the effectiveness performance report is provided in Table 86. For this OT, the main challenge identified refers to the transmission and processing of data and flow between authorities and operators, and not in the provision of the data. This issue could be tackled through the implementation of the E-logbook by the authority in Seychelles. Although progress has been reported towards the implementation of the electronic system, this was reported as delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. MR2 reports of several actions towards the identification of all relevant data protocols and the provision of a report which indicates effective performance for achieving I_1_CS6. Yet, important challenges remain towards achieving I_2_CS6, as reported in MR2, currently standardisation in data collection is an ongoing process. Yet establishing an Electronic Monitoring System (EMS) is still the main obstacle for its implementation. The auditors consider that until this issue is tackled, and specific actions are taken towards the implementation of the system by the national authorities, the indicator would not be achieved.

Table 86 OT 6.1 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_1_CS6 Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the SFPA agreement. - Indicator Cat. C	A report has been published describing the data protocols.	5
I_2_CS6 Standardised fisheries information presented - Indicator Cat. A	The actions reported towards achieving I_1_CS6 are relevant towards advancing in achieving I_2_CS6. However, several important actions are still needed for this indicator to be achieved, regarding the implementation of the E-logbook and adequate reception system and data processing protocols by the national authority.	2
ER Score		3,5

OT 6.2 Catches of non-target species registered in E-logbooks. *Obligatory*

Reporting of bycatch data is considered a broader issue to be tackled at regional level. According to the MR2, the EU fleet is equipped with ERS which allows for reporting on bycatch, although to different levels of detail. Yet, the challenges lay in the reception of the data, as the national authority is not receiving e-logbook data automatically. Struggling to fully implement the ERS system due to the protocol used to exchange data fields between the EU and Seychelles. The auditor team considers that until the ERS is properly implemented, and the data exchange protocols issues solve, the indicator I_3_CS6 will not be effective. For the indicator I_4_CS6, MR2 reports on effective utilisation of the FarFish DLM for two species. Yet as there is no measurable indication of how many species should have been modelled, the auditor cannot fully assess effectiveness performance. The analysis is presented in Table 87.

Table 87 OT 6.2 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_3_CS6 Template for catch protocol for nontarget species to be implemented in E-logbooks – Indicator Cat. C	Initiatives have been taken to address and achieve this indicator, but so far, no template has been developed. Any actions towards achieving this indicator will not be effective until ERS issues are solved.	2
I_4_CS6 Model implementation of DLM to bycatch species - Indicator Cat. B	Modelling of bycatch with DLM has partly been conducted. MR2 reports that the modelling was done for two species. As the indicator does not indicate how many species should be modelled, the auditor cannot fully evaluate the effectiveness of the action. Considering that the modelling was done, and some species reported, the auditor will assign a medium achievement level.	3
ER Score		2,5

OT 6.3 MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected. *Obligatory*

The performance of this OT has been mostly affected by protocol restrictions in sharing VMS data by the fisheries national authority in Seychelles (SFA) and the insufficient AIS data in the area due to the risk of piracy. MR2 reports that there has been progress in identifying the areas where the operator compliance should be analysed. However, the timeframe for conducting this analysis will most likely exceed the lifetime of the FarFish project. The solution suggested is to ensure the continuation of the action after the project, where the task is taken by the SFA directly.

Table 88 OT 6.3 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_5_CS6 Operator compliance verified by analysis of VMS or AIS data for SMSP Initiative – Indicator Cat. C	Although important actions were taken towards advancing in fulfilling this indicator, the VMS and/or AIS data were not available to consider the degree of compliance with the SMSP. The continuation of the action could be taken by the fisheries national authority (SFA)	1
ER score		1

OT 6.4 Updated observer program in place. Recommended

For this OT, MR2 reports mostly developments that have been taken from the side of the authorities in Seychelles, through the implementation of electronic systems and monitoring mechanisms (i.e. CCTV). The auditors find that the text of the progress report, does not provide a clear overview of the actions taken by the FarFish project towards achieving this OT, as the report is mostly on the actions taken by the Seychelles authorities to update their systems.

Moreover, the OT text refers to updating the observer program in place, but the defined indicators aim to establishing it at a regional level. The auditor however, found that there is no clarity with regards to which body could potentially coordinate such a regional observer program. The MR2 suggest an EU-funded project as a possibility, although no further actions are reported to verify whether this is feasible. The auditors, therefore, suggest revising the indicators for OT 6.4, as the regional scope of the indicators appear disconnected from the actions that were taken, in terms of updating the system for the observer program. Furthermore, without clarity on who can coordinate the regional observer program, it is hard to envision any action that can contribute towards the adequate performance of the defined indicators. The performance effectiveness analysis is presented in Table 89.

Table 89 OT 6.4 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_6_CS6 Regional observer program in place – Indicator Cat. C	A National observer program is in place and their systems are being updated by the national authorities. These actions report on adequate performance of the OT, yet do not provide any indication of actions taken towards the performance of the indicators. No clear actions are reported towards this indicator. A regional observer program has not been developed.	1
I_7_CS6 Regional observer program implemented - Indicator	Same as the analysis of I_6_CS6. No clear actions are reported towards this indicator. A regional observer program is not implemented	1
ER Score		1

OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided. Recommended

The OT 6.5 is a recommended target, that answers to the need to improve knowledge about value chain and market conditions of the tuna fisheries in Seychelles. MR2 reports on already available information delivered by the FarFish project (Isaksen et al., 2019). Also, MR2 reports on important actions (e.g. Interviews) planned towards obtaining the information required for the processing and trade for advancing with indicator I_9_CS6. Also, for I_19_CS6, the information for Information concerning the economic impacts and ecological benefits of reducing the number of drifting FADs in Seychelles waters will be collected using a questionnaire to operators. A final report including all results is expected by September 2021.

Table 90 OT 6.5 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_8_CS6 Information on catch and landings provided - Indicator Cat. C	This information is provided in D3.4 in FarFish	5
I_9_CS6 Information on processing and trade provided - Indicator Cat. C	This information is partly presented in D3.4 and will be further expanded in a coming deliverable this fall	4
I_10_CS6 Socio-economic impacts of using drifting FADs provided - Indicator Cat. C	This information is yet not provided, but questionnaires are planned to be conducted this fall	3
ER Score		4

OT 6.6 VMS or AIS signals are transmitted. Recommended

The aim of this OT is to ensure that VMS and/or AIS data is transmitted by the operators. Yet, this OT 6.6 faces the same challenge than OT 6.3, in terms of obtaining the VMS data for conducting the analysis. Furthermore, AIS data is also not available as is common practice to turn off the system in Seychelles waters due to the risk of piracy. MR2 reports the reasons for the restrictions for releasing the data, where SFA is only allowed to provide these data for rescue and prosecution purposes. MR2 also mentioned that the flag states and operators could facilitate access to the data through their correspondent Fisheries Monitoring Centre (FMC). However, no action is reported whether this was pursued or not. The auditor considers that due the importance to obtaining this data for OT 6.6 and OT 6.3, these two targets could be merged to focus all efforts into advancing towards improving the conditions for data sharing within the Seychelles authorities. Efforts should be directed towards requesting that data could be provided exceptionally for research purposes, considering the relevance of the two OTs for improving the monitoring and control within the Seychelles EEZ.

Table 91 OT 6.6 Effectiveness performance evaluation for the indicators and ER score

Indicator	Evaluation	ER Score
I_9_CS6 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with geolocalization - Indicator Cat. B	Data was not available, and no analysis conducted.	2
I_10_CS6 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS), geolocalization - Indicator Cat. B	Data was not available, and no analysis conducted.	2
ER Score		2

C.2 Compliance

This stage of the audit aims to evaluate how the reported information complies with what is specified in the management recommendation. A compliance assessment determines whether the specified criterion for the defined indicators is met. This assessment includes a qualitative and quantitative analysis of completeness, timeliness, and quality of the sources of each indicator. The summary of this analysis will provide a Compliance Index (C.I) that will be reported in the audit summary.

OT 6.1 Harmonised fisheries information system in place. *Obligatory*

For OT 6.1, on the harmonization of the fisheries information system, the MR2 reports that several important actions are ongoing to advance with the implementation of the ERS system by the SFA. This is a crucial step as most of the reported challenges refer to the use of paper-based logbooks by SFA, which is time consuming, and causes discrepancies in catch estimates, as well as a lack of uninterrupted data processing and analysis. The FarFish project has followed on the advances towards the ERS implementation and strived for the harmonization of the systems. Yet some relevant actions are still necessary to achieve this target and the timeline for it seems to surpass the lifetime of the project. The compliance report is provided in Table 92.

Table 92 OT 6.1 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	There is no harmonised fisheries information system in place. Efforts are made and some plans for further implementation are described, yet some relevant actions are still pending to accomplish the target. Most notably the need for the full implementation of the E-logbook by SFA.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	There were no time or frequencies specified for this OT, but MR2 states that this will not be achieved in the lifetime of the FarFish project, and that actions should be taken to ensure continuation of the action after the project's end.	2
Source quality Level (S)	The work so far has been undertaken by the bodies identified as responsible entities (i.e.. SFA, IOTC, SGP)	5
Total CI Score		4

OT 6.2 Catches of non-target species registered in E-logbooks. *Obligatory*

OT 6.2 refers to the registration of non-target species in E-logbooks. As mentioned, the main challenge towards completing this OT in due time is the implementation of an ERS by the Seychelles authorities. The EU operators are equipped to provide the data, although the level of detail varies. The implementation of the DLM for two bycatch species is an important step to improve knowledge on the status of the stocks when data is limited. Yet, until the ERS is fully implemented, important challenges remain to comply with the needed action. Achieving this OT in due time is therefore not considered feasible. Table 93 presents the analysis of the three components of the compliance evaluation for OT 6.2.

Table 93 OT 6.2 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	The implementation of a template for reporting non-target species in the E-logbook is not completed as the ERS is not implemented in Seychelles. Some data have been collected and undertaken (DLM modelling) which contributes to the estimation of stock status. It is not clear whether running the model for only two species is enough to ensure a higher level of completion of the OT.	3
Timeliness Level (T)	There were no time or frequencies specified for this OT. However, it is not reasonable to expect that this will be achieved within the lifetime of FarFish. Actions should be taken to ensure uptake of the OT after the project's end.	2
Source quality Level (S)	The partners involved in the work with this OT are relevant for the implementation, including the SFA, EU operators and FarFish project representatives.	5
Total CI Score		3

OT 6.3 MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP are respected. Obligatory

The main challenge to comply with OT 6.3 was data availability. The provision of either VMS or AIS data was fundamental to conduct any actions towards achieving this OT. Although, some actions were taken to advance in defining the areas for the analysis, the data is fundamental for completion and verification of source quality. Considering that data is not still available the timeliness of the OT is also compromised. Table 94 presents the compliance evaluation for OT 6.3.

Table 94 OT 6.3 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Although some actions have been taken in preparation for the analysis, the OT has not been conducted due to lack of fundamental data for the analysis. Data was not shared due to restrictions by the national authorities for VMS data, and unavailability of AIS data due to security issues.	1
Timeliness Level (T)	This analysis could have taken place within the timeframe of FarFish, but has not been fulfilled	1
Source quality Level (S)	If data had been available, it is reasonable to assume that the analysis would have been performed by the dedicated actor.	1
Total CI Score		1

OT 6.4 Updated observer program in place. Recommended

The auditors team consider that there is a discrepancy between the OT text and the indicators. MR2 reported on advances towards updating the observer program by the national authorities in Seychelles. However, the indicators described the implementation of a regional observer program, for which little is reported in the MR2 document. The compliance analysis is provided in Table 95.

Table 95 OT 6.4 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	The description of activities to a limited degree addresses the indicators, as it focuses mostly on the national observer program. There is a potential mismatch between OT description and defined indicators the auditors were unable to evaluate this.	n/a
Timeliness Level (T)	The regional nature of the indicators of this OT increases the level of complexity and number of actors (national, international and industry) involved. This indicates that this OT will not be achieved within the timeframe of FarFish. Actions were taken towards updating the national systems in Seychelles, although MR2 reports that they deployment will take place after the end of the project. Similarly, to the C analysis, the timeliness (T) component cannot be evaluated.	n/a

Source quality Level (S)	It is not specified who should have the responsibility to perform this activity (some suggestions given e.g. IOC, IOTC).	n/a
Total CI Score		n/a

OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided. Recommended

The MR2 reports several important actions taken and other planned towards achieving the OT 5.6 and its indicators. The compliance analysis is provided in Table 96.

Table 96 OT 6.5 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	Some of the work to complete this OT is delivered, while trade flow and socio-economic aspects of the use of FADs are still pending. MR2 reports that the information will be available through interviews and provision of questionnaires to the operators in the area.	4
Timeliness Level (T)	The results are expected within the FarFish lifetime, even though not specified	4
Source quality Level (S)	So far, the results have been delivered by the responsible partners. MR2 reports on potential interviews to relevant actors in the industry and questionnaires to the operators in the area. These sources are relevant for the purpose of obtaining the information.	4
Total CI Score		4

OT 6.6 VMS or AIS signals are transmitted. Recommended

Like the analysis of OT 6.3, the main challenge to comply with OT 6.6 was data availability. The provision of either VMS or AIS data was fundamental to conduct any actions towards achieving this OT. Table 97 presents the compliance evaluation for OT 6.6.

Table 97 OT 6.6 Compliance evaluation and CI score

Analysis	Evaluation	CI Score
Completeness Level (C)	This OT has not been achieved. Data were not available, and no analysis has been conducted	1
Timeliness Level (T)	It was expected to take place within the timeframe of FarFish, but no analysis has taken place	1
Source quality Level (S)	A partner was designated to perform this task, given data had been made available it is reasonable to assume it would have been performed	1
Total CI Score		1

D. MR Effects

The audit includes an assessment of the economic implications of the OTs. Each of the OTs are discussed below and the results summarised in associated tables.

OT 6.1 Harmonised fisheries information system in place.

The current system lacks harmonization. Although data can be provided by the EY fleet, these data is not dealt with consistently. Lack of data to undertake stock assessment was identified a major challenge for this area. Considering the relevance of the action, the implementation of a harmonized system could have render important benefits for the tune fisheries in Seychelles. Although difficult to foresee, the economically relevant impacts apart from the direct costs associated with the study conducted, can be estimated in relation to the potential improvement of the status of the different stocks from the improved knowledge for stock assessment. The potential costs and benefits from the implementation of this action are suggested in Table 98.

Table 98 OT 6.1 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/ Benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Harmonisation of fisheries information	Cost	Small	FarFish and participants	Incurred
Implementation of harmonised system	Cost	Small to medium - related to efficiency	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Reduced capacity employed	Benefit	Uncertain	Vessel owners	Short-medium and long

Improved control and inspection procedures	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, vessel owners	Short-medium and long
Improved stock assessments	Benefit	Highly uncertain	National authorities, vessel owners, society	Long
Improved stock status	Benefit	Uncertain	National authorities, vessel owners, society	Medium and long
Improved yield from fisheries	Benefit	Highly uncertain	Vessel owners and trickle effects to society	Long

OT 6.2 *Catches of non-target species registered in E-logbooks*

Better registration of non-target species may allow for better stock assessment and enable improved management of these stocks. This may have both ecological and economic benefits. At the same time data collection, analysis and stock management will be costly. Possible management measures implemented to limit catches of these species are likely to lead to costly changes in effort cost for the current fishing fleet. These are highly uncertain. Thus, the net benefit is difficult to discern. The temporal nature of the impacts is also uncertain. Establishing data collection and modelling stocks will incur costs on both short, medium, and long term. Changes to management can also be of the same timeframe. The scale of the impacts is likely to be small compared to the large-scale tuna fisheries.

Table 99 OT 6.2 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Separation of catches	Cost	Small	Vessels	All time scales
Modelling and management of non-target species	Cost	Small	To be decided, but likely authorities and RFMO	All time scales
Yield and effort cost implications of management measures	Uncertain	Uncertain	Vessels, processors, and downstream actors	All time scales

OT 6.3 *Respect MPAs and no-take zones, OT 6.6* *VMS or AIS signals are transmitted*

The FarFish defined components of these OTs have not been reached and would, even if reached, have very small economic impacts. Further work, reaching the intention of the actual OT, may have higher economic impacts. In terms of costs and benefits, it is difficult to assess whether the impact can become a cost or yield a benefit, and the extend of it. Not being allowed to fish in given zones may increase the operational costs of fleets. The positive stock effects from these areas may provide an economic benefit through increased stock size and yield. The former would be a short-, medium-, and long-term issue, while the latter will be a long-term impact. Both will be borne by the fleet but will

through ripple effects and possible fishing fees/taxation also be relevant for society and the processing industry.

Table 100 OT 6.3 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Cost of fishing effort	Cost	Uncertain	Vessels	All time scales
Yield implications from management measures	Benefit	Uncertain	Vessels, processors, and downstream actors	Medium and long-term

OT 6.4 Updated observer program in place

The FarFish components of this OT have not been achieved and the economic impacts are hence very limited. Work is ongoing by SFA and other authorities on these aspects. This work may have both cost and benefit impacts. Especially running an observer programme is costly. The costs, however, are likely to be relatively small compared with the total value added from the fishery. The question of who bears these costs depends on how the programme is implemented – the costs could be levied to the fishing vessels, the authorities or shared between them. They will also be both short, medium, and long term. Other impacts are more difficult to predict but may lead to improvements in management of both target and bycatch stocks.

Table 101 OT 6.4 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Cost of observer programme	Cost	Small	To be decided, but likely authorities and vessels	All time scales
Yield implications from management measures	Uncertain	Uncertain	Vessels, processors, and downstream actors	Medium and long-term

OT 6.5 Trade flow data provided

It is difficult to link any likely direct economic impacts to this OT and the two first indicators specified. There are stronger economic linkages with the third indicator related to FADs. The FarFish-related contribution and cost is very likely to be very limited. However, further work building on this may bring about increased knowledge about socioeconomic aspects of FADs that again may influence management of fisheries. This may have effects on both the yield of fisheries and costs of effort and catch. Effort limitation may increase stock size and sustainable yield, but costs may increase from a less efficient fishery. Thus, the net benefit is uncertain.

Table 102 OT 6.5 MR effects – Cost-Benefit assessment

Impact	Cost/benefit	Impact scale	Stakeholder	Temporal nature
Cost of fishing effort	Cost	Uncertain	Vessels	All time scales
Yield implications from management measures	Benefit	Uncertain	Vessels, processors, and downstream actors	Medium and long-term

8.3 Summary of the Audit

Table 103 presents a summary of the audit of the Seychelles MR2. The outcome targets are not finalised, and some further action will take place within the lifetime of FarFish for some OTs and others must be brought further by relevant FarFish partners beyond the lifetime of the project. At a practical level the OTs and related indicators are scored with a relatively low level of achievements. Some of this should be considered a result of the high ambition of the OTs and indicators, which could not be achieved by the FarFish partners. Some also should be ascribed the audit framework itself. All in all, a lot of good initiatives have been taken place and some might at a later stage be taken up by relevant actors at a national and potentially also, at the regional level.

Table 103 Audit dashboard: Summary of evaluation of CS6 Seychelles MR2

PHASE			OT 6.1	OT 6.2	OT 6.3	OT 6.4	OT 6.5	OT 6.6
Step 1 MR IMPLEMENT.	Documentation system	Crit. 1						
	Documentation system	Crit. 2						
	Sensitivity analysis	Not relevant						
Responsive Assessment								
Step 2 MR PERFORM. EVALUATION	Performance Assessment	ER						
	Compliance Assessment	CI				N/A		
	MR Effects	Not quantifiable	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Progress			On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going	On-going
Audit Summary	Current assessment							
	Final assessment							

9 Final remarks

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools, and methods to support responsible, sustainable, and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction (EEZ) of non-EU coastal states as well as in international waters / high seas. Central to the FarFish concept is the implementation of a practical approach to implement Results-Based Management (RBM) principles, where the resource users are directly involved in the management and decision-making process. A key component of this approach is the audit process which serves the purpose to determine whether the MRs, including the monitoring and documentation measures, are being implemented as agreed. This document presented the results of an intermediate audit on performance of the results reported in the second version of the Management Recommendations (MR2) for six diverse case studies in the FarFish project. The MRs cover two case studies from EU fisheries in the high seas in the Southwest and Southeast Atlantic respectively, as well as four case studies under Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements in Cape Verde, Senegal, Mauritania, and Seychelles. These case studies range from highly complex fisheries in the high seas to single and multispecies fisheries in national waters of the respective coastal states, in some cases with further regional implications.

To draw general conclusions from the audit results is a difficult task considering the diversity and range of complexity between the six case studies. However, the application of this RBM approach demonstrates that there have been substantial advancements in all the case studies, especially with respect to increasing knowledge on methods to assess the stocks, increase capacity and training to scientific observers, and even establishing mechanisms to potentially promote better management of unregulated areas, such as the SW-Atlantic high seas. In all cases, collaboration has been efficient to set outcome targets agreed upon between the operators and authority representatives, identifying suitable indicators to measure these against. This collaboration creates a shared understanding amongst the relevant stakeholders, that further stimulates active involvement that translates into information gathering and sharing and all together, into a more participatory management of the respective fisheries. Also, it was clear that great work was dedicated to the Management Recommendations for all the case studies, as they had been greatly improved following the first audit process.

However, several challenges were also found in the implementation and performance of the MRs. Challenges with data availability were found in several cases, which referred to, for example, data sharing restrictions from the side of the relevant authorities. If properly communicated or identified, these issues could have been tackled prior to setting the targets, favouring the adequate development of some of the actions in the second iteration of the MRs.

More notable for the four SFPAs CS, was the clear difference in the success of the actions where adequate coordination and collaboration was in place with the Coastal States. This outcome

demonstrates that the success of the RBM approach is highly depended on the involvement and active participation of the implicated parties, where both are equally motivated and aware of the importance of their involvement to accomplish the targets.

The audit process was conducted to the extent that the Management Recommendations were reported. Therefore, results of some actions relevant for the OTs were not yet available including self-sampling results and value chain analysis reports. A final MR version is expected within the lifetime of the FarFish project, as there is continuous work on several of the actions that will be updated as work progresses towards achieving the OTs. However, it will not be possible to conduct an ex-post evaluation and final audit within the lifetime of the project due to time constraints and contractual specifications within the research and innovation action framework. However, what remains is that great advancements have been made towards the implementation of the RBM to fisheries where co-management has proven effective, when both parties are equally involved, to improve data and knowledge, tools and methods that support responsible, sustainable, and profitable fisheries within these case study areas.

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